

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B410
 Date: 29 Oct 2008
 Take Off: 09:59:43
 Landing: 15:16:13
 Flight Time 5h 16m 30s

Campaign: VOCALS

Operating Area: South east pacific ocean off west coast of northern Chile

POB	Position	Name	Institute	Logs y/n
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight	
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay Rae	Directflight	
3	CCM1	Tracey Hill	Directflight	
4	Mission Scientist 1	Keith Bower	Manchester University	
5	Mission Scientist 2	Phil Brown	Met Office	
6	Mission Scientist 3	Paul Barrett	Met Office	
7	Flight Manager	Jim Crawford	FAAM	
8	Core Chem /FTP	Doug Anderson	FAAM	
9	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office	
10	SWS/SHIMS	Debbie O'Sullivan	Met Office	
11	CCN	Jamie Trembath	FAAM	
12	ARIES	Stuart Rogers	Met Office	
13	AMS/SP2	Paul Williams	Manchester University	
14	Wet neph/psap	Dave Tiddeman	Met Office	
15	VACC	Mark Bart	Leeds University	
16	Manchester cloud	Jonny Crosier	Manchester University	
17	CVI	James Bowles	Met Office	
18	MARSS	- unmanned -		

Flight Track:

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B410
 Date: 29 October 2008
 Project: VOCALS
 Location: South East Pacific off coast of Chile

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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093127		gin	0.11 kft	023	started
095452		ASP	0.10 kft	018	open
095943		T/O	0.08 kft	198	Arica
100023	101012	Profile 1	0.56 - 10.0 kft	217	start at t/o
100229		heimann	2.7 kft	220	open
100337		cloud tops	3.8 kft	223	
100732		JW	7.5 kft	224	on
100820		JW	8.2 kft	224	zero
100835		Nev	8.5 kft	224	zero
100954		heimann	9.9 kft	221	cal06
101227		transit	10.0 kft	223	fl100
101342		twc	10.0 kft	226	power cycled
101803	102928	Profile 2	10.0 - -.04 kft	225	50ft
102338		!	4.2 kft	225	cloud top
102427		!	3.3 kft	229	cloud base
102928	103017	Profile 3	-.04 - 0.36 kft	222	50ft 500ft
103017	103351	Run 1	0.36 kft	219	500ft point Alpha
103352	104453	Run 2.1	0.36 - 0.46 kft	240	point Alpha
103624		heimann	0.38 kft	266	cal 10
103633		bbr	0.42 kft	266	retract
104453	104708	Profile 4	0.46 - 2.8 kft	267	
104708	105900	Run 2.2	2.8 - 2.4 kft	267	
104749		r2.2	2.7 kft	263	drop to 2500 to clear cloud base
104818		r2.2	2.4 kft	269	restarted 2500ft
105900	110000	Profile 5	2.4 - 3.4 kft	265	
110001	111051	Run 2.3	3.4 kft	264	
111051	111245	Profile 6	3.4 - 5.5 kft	264	
111245	112036	Profile 7	5.5 - -.07 kft	267	50ft
111347		JW	4.8 kft	267	zero
111402		nev	4.4 kft	268	zero
111940		qnh	0.25 kft	266	1019
112037	112116	Profile 8	-.07 - 0.29 kft	268	50ft 500ft
112116	113207	Run 3.1	0.29 - 0.31 kft	265	500ft
113208	113416	Profile 9	0.31 - 1.8 kft	266	
113417	114515	Run 3.2	1.8 - 1.9 kft	267	
114515	114707	Profile 10	1.9 - 3.8 kft	268	
114707	115749	Run 3.3	3.8 kft	263	
115750	120002	Profile 11	3.8 - 5.7 kft	263	reversal 5900
120002	120712	Profile 12	5.7 - -.13 kft	268	reversal 5900
120431		qnh	1.5 kft	271	1020
120712	120747	Profile 13	-.13 - 0.26 kft	269	
120747	121832	Run 4.1	0.26 - 0.36 kft	268	
121833	122153	Profile 14	0.36 - 3.7 kft	265	
122154	123312	Run 4.2	3.8 - 2.8 kft	267	
122237		r42	3.6 kft	267	drop 700ft to remain below inversion
122311		r4.2	2.9 kft	264	restated at 3000'
122407		r4.2	2.9 kft	264	'cloud run' but mostly clear
122608		r4.2	2.8 kft	279	turning eastwards
122810		!	2.9 kft	027	79 56 most westerly point
123313	124616	Profile 15	2.8 - 14.3 kft	105	
124616	130119	Profile 16	14.3 - -.12 kft	081	
125557		cloud	4.4 kft	089	top
125653		cloud	3.4 kft	092	bottom
130120	130158	Profile 17	-.12 - 0.28 kft	088	
130159	131256	Run 5.1	0.28 - 0.30 kft	084	
130255		r 5.1	0.30 kft	090	500ft
131257	131423	Profile 18	0.30 - 1.6 kft	086	

131423	132526	Run 5.2	1.6 - 1.3 kft	085
131442		r 5.2	1.3 kft	085 pop down to clear cloud
131452		r 5.2	1.3 kft	084 start
131539		r 5.2	1.3 kft	082 below cloud run 1500ft
132526	132806	Profile 19	1.3 - 3.7 kft	088
132807	133810	Run 5.3	3.7 - 3.6 kft	091
132832		r5.3	3.7 kft	092 in cloud run
133811	134030	Profile 20	3.6 - 5.6 kft	083
133921		cloud	4.7 kft	085 tops
134031	134212	Profile 21	5.6 - 4.1 kft	091
134212	135359	Run 5.4	4.1 - 5.3 kft	090
134810		r 5.4	4.1 kft	086 overhead Ron Brown
135400	135418	Profile 22	5.3 - 5.5 kft	096
135418	140217	Profile 23	5.5 - -.10 kft	098 50ft
135511		!	4.7 kft	097 end 5.4 start p22 late log
135534		cloud	4.3 kft	099 top
135841		qnh	1.4 kft	102 1019
140218	140246	Profile 24	-.12 - 0.27 kft	101 50ft
140247	141340	Run 6.1	0.27 - 0.36 kft	100
140331		r 6.1	0.37 kft	104 500ft
141340	141610	Profile 25	0.36 - 2.7 kft	101
141610	142640	Run 6.2	2.7 kft	098
141642		r 6.2	2.8 kft	099 below cloud
142641	142826	Profile 26	2.7 - 3.7 kft	099
142826	143925	Run 6.3	3.7 kft	102
142914		r 6.3	3.7 kft	089 3800ft in cloud
143456		!	3.6 kft	060 point Alpha
143925	144039	Profile 27	3.7 - 5.0 kft	049
144039	144702	Profile 28	5.0 - -.05 kft	045 50 ft
144208		cloud	3.8 kft	047 tops 4200
144703	144731	Profile 29	-.06 - 0.29 kft	050 50 ft
144732	145731	Run 7.1	0.29 - 0.38 kft	048
144838		r 7.1	0.36 kft	048 500ft
145732	145949	Profile 30	0.38 - 3.5 kft	046
150019	150956	Run 7.2	3.5 kft	045
151613		Land	0.04 kft	019 Arica
151814		ASP	0.08 kft	200 closed

B410 Track 29-OCT-08

VOCALS Flight B410
FAAM sortie brief

Weds 29 October, 2008

T/O **07:00 local**
Land **c. 12:00 local**

Operating Area: South East Pacific Ocean, off the west coast of northern Chile, along latitude line 20S

Point Alpha: 72°W 20°S

Point Beta: 79°30'W 20°S

Sortie Objectives: To sample aerosol and Sc cloud as a function of distance from the coast to the pristine background

Weather: High pressure system off shore capping a marine boundary layer with widespread Sc cloud. Near shore marine boundary layer winds from SSW.

Flight patterns:

1. Take off and profile ascent 1000 ft/min immediately to 6,000 ft amsl to check instrumentation. At Mission Scientist discretion, continue profile ascent to FL100 before profile descending to 50' at 1000 ft/min
[25 min; T=0h 25 min]
2. Continue to point **Alpha** either in cloud or below cloud at 500 ft
[0 min; T=0h 25 min]
3. On westerly heading, profile ascent to 1000ft above cloud top.
4. Perform cycle consisting of
 - a. profile descent to 50ft amsl,
 - b. climb to 500ft below cloudbase,
 - c. 10-min straight/level leg,
 - d. climb to 500ft below cloud top,
 - e. 10-min straight/level leg,
 - f. profile ascent to 1000ft above cloud top.
 - g. At Mission Scientist discretion, an additional 10 min leg may be included in this cycle at 100ft amsl.
5. Repeat item 4 until arrival at point Beta, at which point turn onto easterly heading.
6. Following completion of one cycle, at Mission Scientist discretion, profile ascent to FL150 followed by profile descent to 50ft amsl, and then resume cycles of straight/level legs as per item 4.
7. Repeat item 4 along return leg to point Alpha, and continue as far as possible along recovery leg from point Alpha to Arica.

VOCALS Flight B410 (20°S Cross Section Flight #2) (29/10/2008)

Mission Scientist Debrief : Keith N Bower

Mission summary

Take off from Arica at 10.00z was followed by an immediate profile ascent at 1000ft/min (to FL100) on track towards point Alpha (20S 72W). After a short straight and level run (SLR) in transit towards alpha (FL100) a profile descent to 50ft (at 1000ft/min to 1000ft thereafter 500ft/min to 50ft) was undertaken and followed by an immediate climb back to 500ft amsl to start SLR R1 to point Alpha. At Alpha the aircraft turned to head west continuing at 500ft amsl along 20S to carry out a 10min SLR R2.1, which was then followed by SLR R2.2 in clear air below CB, initially at 2800ft. It was clear that there was much more inhomogeneity in the cloud compared to the previous 20S mission (B408), with bases of Cu extending down below the background SCu bases. This classic decoupling became even more pronounced to the west. To enable CVI flow calibrations to be made in clear air, the altitude of R2.2 was reduced by 400ft to avoid the Cu bases. However the calibration was affected by the presence of drizzle drops which increased in concentration through the run. A 10min SLR, R2.3 was carried out in cloud at 3500ft. Drizzle concentrations here were reported to increase to 30 per litre (from 10). Curiously the SMPS on the CVI reported a peak in the size distribution at around 20nm whereas below cloud there were many more aerosols which peaked at 200-300nm in the accumulation mode. Cloud droplet concentrations were reported to be 150-200 per cc (mean diameter 17um) by CDP, 125-150 per cc by FSSP (mean dia 14-15um) but in higher concentrations (300-350 per cc) by the CAS in CAPS (mean dia 13-15um). CAPS liquid water content (LWC) was reported as high as 0.3-0.5 g/m³, while the Lyman Alpha hygrometer on the CVI reported a value of 0.15 g/m³. J-W LWC values appeared to be higher (at least 50% in one spot check). It was considered the presence of drizzle may have caused the CVI flows to have been set too high, possibly missing some of the smaller drops. The CVI enrichment factor of 25 was also lower than on previous flights and so the flows used on previous flights were then adopted for the remainder of the flight. NO_x values peaked below CB at 7ppb. Following R2.3 a profile ascent up to 1000ft above CT was carried out. CT was seen to be around 4600ft.

The cycle of profiling down from 1000ft above CT to 50ft amsl, followed by a series of 10 min SLRs at 500ft amsl, at another level 300-500ft below CB and in-cloud 300-500ft below CT (SLRs separated by profile ascents/descents) was repeated (with variations) twice more on the outbound leg and 3 times on the return leg from the most westerly point Bravo (which was 20S 79deg57minW). Upon turning at Bravo, a profile ascent up to FL150 was carried out to investigate the presence of any layering above the level of CT, however little layering structure was seen above the inversion.

The decoupling and corresponding in-homogeneity in cloud structure sometimes made it difficult to estimate Sc CB. However, the observation from previous flights that the whole cloud deck lifted the further west traveled was again seen. CT height increased from ~4300ft (cycle 1 and 2) to 4600ft cycle 3. CBs were around 3000ft closer to the coast increasing to around 4000ft towards Bravo. However beyond 78deg30min W a

cloud free rift like structure was encountered up to the turn. Aerosol size distributions were seen to be bimodal in this zone (peaks at 45nm and >150nm) while PCASP concentrations fell from the 200/cc seen in the first cycle to around 50 -55 (cycles 2 and 4) to around 40 per cc near Bravo. Similarly the cloud droplet concentration of 150-200 observed in cycle 1 dropped to below 70/cc in cycle 4. The rift like region at 80W and beyond was particularly clean with low aerosol numbers together with a reduction in sulphate loading as seen by AMS and VACC. The latter saw little sodium chloride at any time. 2DC drizzle concentrations were observed to be a lot higher in the last but one cycle 5. These were higher than 100 per litre during incloud run R5.3. Finally during the final cycle (after passing ALPHA) before landing, substantial increases in mass loadings and aerosol numbers were observed. Sub and supermicron aerosol (SMPS and CAS) concentrations increased by a factor of 3, CCN concentrations increased by >30% and a corresponding 8ppb decrease in O3 concentration was observed. At the same time the cloud layer thinned to around ~500-600ft deep. The aircraft landed at Arica at 15:16z

Instrumentation

CVI : zeros below cloud (ie flows set to lead to zero aerosol concentration in the absence of cloud droplets) were troublesome due to the presence of drizzle, while zeros above cloud were good. Still no CPC on the CVI. Flows for previous flights used.

Wet-Neph : mostly OK, but brief period of lost data (due to comms error)

SWS/ARIES/MARSS : good throughout

SHIM : upper OK lower not working

AMS : fine

SMPS : OK up to a certain altitude

Core chemistry ; CO NO_x SO₂ Ozone all fine

CCN : no data on outbound leg (leak from cabin) but fine on return leg

Water CPC : fine throughout flight

VACC : perfect

Cloud microphysics:

PCASP : seems to need a clean. Extra counts seen in channel 1 needs investigating further

Backup FSSP and CDP swapped over which was seeing the higher concentration but generally these and other microphysical probes were OK

PCIP-15 (known faulty before takeoff)

LWC JW and Nevzorov : good throughout.

2DS : fine

CAPS : fine

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B.410... Date 29/10/08... Name K.N.BOWER... Page 1 of 10

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
6.45.37	(KNB) -	6:47.54			Station 1 - 4
6.52.04	(KNB time - noted)				Pwr transfer
6.54.04					Taxi
6.59.24					Rolling
7.00.00	≡	09 59 43	z		T/O
					CB, - Very Grey! 2 SSDA.
					1013
					CT - 3500 ft
09.59.43	P1				fm T/O
10.10.09	P1 end	FL100	220	18°48'/10°48'	SLR transit before start of probe down - to Wet Neph - enable instruments/operators to Setup: AMS scans - satellite already.
10.15.02	P2 start	FL100	225	19°12'/11°12'	Profile down to SOFT towards α 10.34°/21.7°C 697mb hmb/208°
10.23.42	P2	4000	224	19°30'/11°30'	CT 4300 ft 872mb, 7.68/-17.67
10.24.29	P2	3200	229	19°30'/11°30'	CB 3300 ft
					QNH 1017 mb
					Neph $\Rightarrow$ layer 7500 - 6000
10.29.27	P2/P3	50ft	222	19°45'/11°42'	16.8°C/10.68°C 1016mb Smps/201°
10.30.14	R1.0 st	500 ft	219	19°45'/11°48'	End P3 - Start SLR 15.6°/9.64°C 1001mb P CASE 200, m 20-25 $\uparrow$ CT Seeing 3/8 high SOCs - Acc. Mode: 300m
10.33.52	R2.1	500 ft	turn.	α	End R1, turned to start R2.1 - QNH 1018

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B...41D... Date 29/10/08 Name K. N. Bower Page 2 of 10

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
10:49:30					CAS ~ 7/μm ³ ↑ 0.6 μm (but values > 3 μm)
					- looking up - some inhomogeneities in cloud
10:44:52	R2.1E/ P4	500ft	267	20°0'/72°42'	996mb 14.85°/10.08° 8mb/175°
10:47:00	P4E/ R2.2	2800	267	20°0'/72°48'	Stabilizing run - in CB's - dropping down wt SO ₂ - not seeing NaCl.
10:48:17	R2.2	2400	269	20°0'/72°54'	Restarted run at 2500ft to clear Cu CB - in CN cloud
				(926mb 8.61°/8.08° Smps/160°)	CEN - mostly dry CEN CPC - CN ~ 300-330 cm ⁻³ CEN ~ 5 MBu 3 - CN seems large - so plus to high because of this - zero particle flux will loose drops
10:58:57	end 2.2 / start PS		265	20°0'/73°42'	927mb 8.61°/8.45° 7mb/159° CB at 300
10:51:51	end PS / R2.3 start	3500	266	20°0'/73°42'	In cloud 895mb 8.22°/7.63° 7mb/152° higher drizzle 10/l → 30/l. sec NO _x 7mb - just below the CT CNI enriched to 25 AMS - on CNI scales peak at 20nm monomodal below CB - large stuff centered at 300nm -

660

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Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B...410... Date 29/10/08 Name K.N. BOWEN Page 3 of 10

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
					ODP 150 - 200 ϕ 17 μ m
					FS... 125 - 150 ϕ 15 - 14 μ m
					CAS - 13 - 15 μ m CMCS 300-350 μ m ²
					not seen lot of
					LWC 0.5 g/m (0.3-0.5 g/m ²)
					OVF LWC 0.13 or 0.125
					JW numbers (stated - but seems higher to me)
11.10.49	2.3 ^{cont} /P6	3400	265	20°0'/74°30'	894mb 6.5°/9.1°C 10m/s/157°
11.11.50	P6	4400	266	20°0'/74°36'	4600' = CT 861mb 3.89°/7.36° 9m/s/147°
11.11.50	P6	4600H			CT Climbing to 1000' above CT.
11.12.42	P6/P7 ^{sl}	5400H	267	20°0'/74°30'	P6 and P7 start at 5600H (Stronger T/Tid?) 10.2/23.8°
11.13.56	P7	4600H	266	20°0'/74°42'	CT = 4600' again 15.32°/-25.2° 7m/s/147° 856mb
11.15.16	P7	3000H	261	20°0'/74°48'	CD = 3100H 6.71°/8.38° 11m/s/146° 905mb
					NO _x
					Peak just under 2ppb NO ₂ above
					(0.5ppb background)
					1019 QNH
11.20.31	P7 ^{cont} /P8 ^{sl}	500H	265	20°0'/75°12'	1015 mb 16.47°/10.52° 10m/s/149°
					Descent: large drizzle drops $\uparrow$ 700 μ m
					PCASP 40-50 cm ² ?
					CN ~ 200
					CCN ~ 10 at 0.2%
11.21.14	P8 ^{cont} /P8.1	500H	265	20°0'/75°12'	CN / SMPs Conc lower (1003mb 11m/s/152°)
					SO ₂ lower, VALL also (+15.22/10.55)

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B.....410 Date 29/10/08 Name KN BOWER Page 4 of 10

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
					Blip in Nephelometer
11.26.30	sh				Blip in CPC - doubling concentration
					Blip in VALL also here
					ZDS - some drizzle
(500) 11.32.04	R3.1g/P9 [300A]		265	20°0/76°0	Climbing to dr run at 2600 (from 500ft)
(2000) 11.34.13	P9end/R3.2	1800'	267	20°0/76°12'	CB lower here - so next run at 2000ft
11.37.13					ZDS - some drizzle
					CPC ⇒ 7 drizzle events
11.44.00					lot of drizzle here
11.45.12	R3.2a/P10	1800'	268	20°0/76°54'	946mb 10.69°/11.28°C 10m/s/149°
(2000) 11.45.12	R3.2c/P10s	1800'	268	20°0/76°54'	Cloud base very variable - inhomogeneous break up ← ?
(3000) 11.47.03	P10c/R3.3sh	3700'	263	20°0/77°6'	883mb 6.23/7.97°C 12m/s/152°
					SP2 - sees particles - not necessarily high
					High mass Org, + Sulphate
					Particle chert - peaks 20nm (ok CVI ??) ✖
					(Vol dust 300nm)
11.53.23	R3.3	3800	265	19°54/77°30	Wile in cloud here 881mb 5.35/6.76° 12m/s/158°
11.54.00	R3.3				Local CB is above us - a hole (avoid)
					Drop N° - Comes CPP 150 - 50 range
(4000) 11.57.47	R3.3E/P11s	3700	264	19°54/77°45'	882mb 6.08°/7.07°C 11m/s/150° P11 starts in a hole
11.58.56	P11	4600	264	19°54/77°54'	CT @ 4900 ft 886mb 3.88/6.57° 9m/s/140°
(5000) 11.59.58	P11E/P12g	5600	268	20°00/78°0'	821mb 14.35°/-26.86 4m/s/116° big change T/Td
(4000) 12.01.20	P12	4600	261	20°0/78°6'	CT, 852mb 5.27°/-15.43° 10m/s/152°
(4000) 12.02.16	P12	3700	263	20°0/78°12'	CB 3800 - 4000 ft 884mb -6.50°/12.31° 10m/s/146°

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B...410 Date 29/10/08 Name K.N. BOWER Page 5 of 10

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
					1020 QNH
					PRB - Classic decoupling - - - -
					RL decoupling - T structure M5x2
					Cu below Sc base - - - -
12.07.06	R2 and / P13	[500ft]	268°	20°0'/76°30'	12m/s/144° 1017mb 16.9°/11.59°
12.07.44	P13 and / R4.1	[500ft]	268	19°54'/76°36'	11m/s/144° 1008mb 15.99/11.46
12.10:30	R4.1	[500ft]			Big hole ahead here (rift?)
					No cloud above us at all
					AMS - SAMS - bimodal below
					Peaks: at 46 and >100 min.
					Lines 'really low
					PCASP = 55
					CN = 280
					CCN = ? low level Max CCN 0.5% very lt
12.18.33	R4.1 and / R4.3	500ft			(Profile to where cloud would have been) 12m/s/147° 1000mb
(3000) 12.21.56	P14 and / R4.25	3700	267	19°54'/77°30'	Aborted - above the Inversion 853mb
(3000) 12.23.09	R4.2	2900	264	19°54'/77°36'	Restarted run at 3000ft - below inv 911mb 8.71/5.87°
					CEN results - less CCN at 0.6% than in POC (expected 80% act here - now less than 10%
					PCASP - 40 cm ³
					CAS - 4 cm ³
					Uber den here - Sea ↓
(3000) 12.23.10	R4.25 / P15	2800	105	19°48'/77°36'	913mb 8.85/6.0 10m/s/134°
12.25.47	R4.2	2800	263	19°54'/77°46'	913mb 9.07/6.2°C 11m/s/146°

79.56

RB @ 19° 38.4835 - Overpass in cloud - Me
79° 46.894° W

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B.....410 Date 29/10/08 Name K.N. BOWER Page 6 of 10

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
12.46.20	P5cont/ P16 start	15000			Not seen much alt - MSci 2 → high Td than previous flight
12.55.39	P16	4900			CT NO ₂ peak, Sx background at CB CBN PCASP - 55-60 cm ⁻³
12.56.32	P16	3900			CB
13.01.18	P16cont/ P17 start	5000			
13.01.56	P17 0.5	5000	84	19°48'/77°36'	1022mb 15.66/9.66 8m/s/135° MSci 2 - see Cu below S Cu base
13.11.22					Cum Cloud - Drizzle - Drizzle on screen too
(500) 13.11.52	S.1cont/ P15 start	3000	87	19°48'/76°54'	CB is very variable - by 2000ft
(800) 13.14.18	P16cont	1500	86	19°48'/76°48'	Tra high to clear CB - drop ↓ (95cm)
(1500) 13.14.40	R5.2 s	1300	85	19°48'/76°48'	95cm 12.14°C/9.5°C 10m/s/125° 14 miles N of E-W track. - to avoid RB in cloud
13.25.24	S.2cont/ P19	1300	88	19°42'/76°6'	966mb 12.24/9.63°C 9m/s/140°
13.26.39					Drizzle - variable CB - Cu base ~ 2600
(3000) 13.28.08	P19cont/ R5.3	3700	91	19°42'/76°0'	2600 too near CT - bumps.
13.30.10	R5.3	3700			Big hole here (not through cloud - but NO cloud) YACC saw SO ₂ < little Sea Salt last run below CB.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B.....410 Date 29/10/08 Name K. N. BOWER Page 7 of 10

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
	R5.3				One Cloud P5SP 50 cm ² $\phi = 13$ CDP 70 $\phi = 18$ 2DC drizzle drop cons lot higher >100/l CCN - N ^o s making more snow. now CAS - 250 drops - 20 μ m (not seeing much drizzle though) LWC = 0.5 g/m ³ (CN = 5.1, @ 0.1% 50/200CN)
13.38.05	R5.3end/P20	3600	83	19°36'/75°24'	886mb 6.08°/8.85° 9m/s/119°
13.39.18	P20	4600	86	19°36'/75°18'	CT 4900ft. 855mb 3.66°/6.47° 8m/s/144°
13.40.28	P20end/P21	5600	91	19°36'/75°12'	↘ 5900ft 825mb 16.01°/27.68° 2m/s/87°
(4000) 13.41.46	P21/	4600	86	19°36'/75°6'	CT ~ 4900 855mb 5.18°/21.1°C 6m/s/123°
(4300) 13.42.09	P21end/P5.4	4100	90	19°30'/75°6'	4300 870mb 4.9°/-0.4°C 7m/s/131°
					One Cloud - Cirrus same - CDP always ϕ higher than P5SP - now reversed. ?? CV1 LWC 0.29 - about half JW. CAS 20 μ 400cm (300-500) LWC = 0.6 JW = 0.5 Nev 0.35
13.52.27	R5.4end P22.5	4100	104	19°36'/74°30'	871mb 4.8°/8.1°C 7m/s/113°
(4700) 13.52.55	P22	4400	104	19°36'/74°30'	CT 4700 861mb 4.03°/7.7°C 8m/s/127°
(4700) 13.54.06	P22/P23	5600	96	19°36'/74°24'	↘ 5700 825mb 15.56°/29.8° 4m/s/46°
(4700) 13.55.16	P23	4600	98	19°36'/74°18'	CT 4700 855mb 14.71°/34.74°C 6m/s/95°
(4100) 13.57.11	P23	2600	104	19°36'/74°12'	CT 2900 916mb 7.93°/8.77° 7m/s/125°
					QNH 1019
13.48.08	R5.4	4100	86°	19°30'/74°42'	871mb 4.87°/8.09° 6m/s/128° Overhaul K1B

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B.410

Date 29/10/08

Name K. N. BOWER

Page 8 of 10

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
					Double CN ants 60/300 CN here
14.01.20					precip 30/400 at highest W. part
14.02.15	P23e/P24g	700ft	101	19°42'/75°54'	1017mb 16.32/10.76°C 5m/s/143°
14.02.44	R6.1st	500ft	100	19°42'/75°54'	end P24 1003mb 15.42/10.4°C 6m/s/143°
14.08.15h					CO went up 5ppb or so last minute
					Good clear SO ₂ transition no organics (VACE) - little sea salt.
					PCASP -110
					AMS - 5MPS not much <100nm mode - 200-300nm peak
					CN advanced back 4 → cash
(2900) 14.16.08	P25i/R6.2b	2600ft	99°	19°48'/75°6'	below CB (main) - in Cu base at base Drizzle - 100µm rainfall - 0.2/cm ³ CircAul 10/like 200µm CB is above - but we are in hole. CircAul FSSP - indicates some late cloud lot of SO ₂ here - staying here at this alt - dipping down to avoid Cu base - back up now
(2900) 14.26.38	R6.2e/P26	2900	99°	19°54'/72°30'	- In cloud on P26 at 14.27.12 (3200ft)
14.28.23	R6.3s	3800			In cloud on - P26end (dropped down from 4320 to base in cloud) FSSP = 150 $\bar{\Phi}$ = 13 CDP = 200 $\bar{\Phi}$ = 17µm 60/like 200 2DS - CBS 330-400 13µm LWC 0.3 CBS drop → 1000

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B.410.....

Date 29/10/08.....

Name K. N. BOWER.....

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Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
(3800) 14.34.50	R6.3	3600	73°	19°34'/72°0'	Turn at α - dead to the left - can see through boss at line - and v. bright above
(3800) 14.39.22	R6.3aw / P27sl	3600	49°	19°46'/71°42'	RECOVER
14.41.51	P27	3700			4200 CT
14.42.		3500			
(4200) 14.39.43	P27	3900	47°	19°46'/71°42'	CT 4200 875mb 5.9°C/7.19°C 3m/s/346°
14.40.36	P27/aw / P28a	2900	45°	19°42'/71°42'	5200 ft, dead P28 ↓ 17.95/25.2°C 4m/s/335
(4200) 14.41.51	P28	3900	44°	19°42'/71°36'	CT 4200ft. 878mb 12.28/-33.56°C 4m/s/345°
(3600) 14.42.34	P28	3300	44°	19°36'/71°36'	CB 3600ft 897mb 8.0/4.87°C 3m/s/2°
14.47.01	P28/aw. / P28a	500ft	50	19°30'/71°24'	End P28, start P29 up to 500 ft
14.47.01	R7.1sl	500	48	19°24'/71°24'	1002mb 16.46/10.94°C 2m/s/168°
					CN counts ↑ 3x
					large (CAS) aerosol ↑ 3x
14.57.30	R7.1aw / P30	500			big step change in ac moments here: CEN ↑ by 1/3 "
14.59.21	P30	2800	47	19°0'/70°54'	CB 913mb 9.96/9.71° 0/245° increase in PCKSP
					drop of 4ppb in O ₃ in last 10 minutes multiple Aerosol
(3600) 14.59.49	P30aw / R7.2sl	3500ft	42	19°0'/70°48'	At CT - dropping down to be in dead down 100 to be in dead
	R7.2.	3400			coming down into dead after bus is CT 200 ft.
	R7.2aw	3300			

7/10 8.10 Lead. Tommas

CVI - zero below cloud turbulence - don't
above cloud good zeros - still no CPC.
(NO CPC - put back on)

Wet Neb - mostly OK - best record last com

Alles - m

SWS - OK

SCAMS - still not work

AMS - fine

SMPS - OK up to certain altitude (cut numbers at 10,000ft)

Core Chem - all fine
CO
SO₂
NO_x
O₃

Core Anal PCASO - needs a clean

- extra carts in ch 1 - doesn't look right
- maybe a problem

- moved when FSSP run CDP - saw and saw sigs
no hard disk crashes

AMS OK

Mars OK

CCN - 1st half flight - sampled certain air 1st half
WPCP - throughout flight all of 2nd half OK.

VACE - perfect

ZDS - fine

CAPS - fine

Plot - Microsoft Internet Explorer

Flight B410 10:10:09
Heading 220 deg Speed 264 knots Height 10.0kft Press 696mb
Lat 18°48.0'S Long 70°48.0'W Wind 3 ms-1/ 227 deg
Temp 8.58C Dewpoint -13.41C

T_Td Plot From: 09:40:09 To: now last 30 mins

Save plot parameters as T_Td

X 515.TIME FROM MIDNIGHT (secs)

525.EQUIVALENT POTENTIAL TEMP (K)
526.REFRACTIVE INDEX (Nunits)
527.POTENTIAL TEMPERATURE (K)
528.DRY AIR DENSITY (kg m-3)
529.DEW POINT (deg C)
530.VAPOUR PRESSURE (mb)
531.MOIST AIR DENSITY (kg m-3)
532.SPECIFIC HUMIDITY (kg kg-1)

Y1 521.DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP (deg C) Black Line Del
Y2 529.DEW POINT (deg C) Red Line Del

End P1

P2 start FL100 - 50ft

Flight B410 10:19:11
 Heading 225 deg Speed 256 knots Height 8.8kft Press 729mb
 Lat 19°18.0'S Long 71°12.0'W Wind 1 ms-1/ 291 deg
 Temp 11.44C Dewpoint -11.88C
 From 09:49:01 to now

Current values
 STATIC PRESSURE 729.31 mb
 DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP 11.45 deg C
 DEW POINT -11.89 deg C

Flight B410 10:22:55
 Heading 224 deg Speed 240 knots Height 4.9kft Press 845mb
 Lat 19°30.0'S Long 71°24.0'W Wind 3 ms-1/ 289 deg
 Temp 19.15C Dewpoint -25.11C
 From 09:52:41 to now

Current values
 PRESSURE HEIGHT 4.92 Kft
 NEPH BLUE SP 5.61 m-1
 NEPH GREEN SP 5.99 m-1
 NEPH RED SP 2.81 m-1

CT 4300ft

CB 3300ft

P2 end 50ft start P3

End P3 start R1 at 500ft

End R2.1 start P5

End P5, R2.2 start but in cloud - dropping down

Restarted R2.2 at 2500ft to clear CB for CVI flow cal -

End R2.2 - start P5 to 3500

P5 end R2.3 start includ at 3500

Plot - Microsoft Internet Explorer

Flight B410 11:10:49
 Heading 285 deg Speed 231 knots Height 3.4kft Press 894mb
 Lat 20°0.0'S Long 74°30.0'W Wind 10 ms-1/ 157 deg
 Temp 6.5C Dewpoint 9.1C

LWC Plot From: 11:00:49 To: now last 10 mins

Save plot parameters as LWC

X 515.TIME FROM MIDNIGHT (secs)

654.OH INST	(1E6)
655.THETA W	(K)
656.JO1D	(E-5/S)
657.TECO NO	(ppb)
658.TECO NO2	(ppb)
659.TECO NOx	(ppb)
660.NEVZOROV LIQUID WATER	(g m-3)
661.NEVZOROV TOTAL WATER	(g m-3)

Y1 535.JAW LIQUID WATER CONTENT (g m-3) Black Line Del

Y2 660.NEVZOROV LIQUID WATER (g m-3) Red Line Del

End R2.3 start P6

P6 CT at 4600ft

P6 end P7 start 5600ft

P7 in cloud again

P7 CB ~3100ft

P7 end 50ft P8 start

P8 end R3.1 start at 500ft

R3.1 end P9 start

P9 end R3.2 start at 2000ft

**Layers below CB - maybe
 the drizzle is cause**

New plot, same times

Flight B410 11:37:40
Heading 267 deg Speed 219 knots Height 1.8kft Press 947mb
Lat 20°0.0'S Long 76°24.0'W Wind 10 m/s-1/ 154 deg
Temp 10.81C Dewpoint 8.74C
From start to now

Current values

—	TIME FROM MIDNIGHT	41859	secs	☐	All	☒	sc
—	NEPH BLUE SP	9.08	m-1	☐			
—	NEPH GREEN SP	9.17	m-1	☐			
—	NEPH RED SP	8.99	m-1	☐			
—	TECO NOx	-0.26	ppb	☐			

End R 3.2

End p10 start R3.3

R3.3 in cloud

Hole in cloud

End R3.3 P11 start at 4000ft in a hole

CT at 4900ft

End P11 start P12

P12 CT at 4900ft

P12 CB 4000ft-3800ft

P12 end 50ft, P13 start

P13 end start R4.1

R4.1 end P14 start to 3900ft where cloud would have been

End P14 start R4.2 at 3900ft

R 4.2 restart at 3000ft

Turning point - most W point 79deg 56

Popped through inv until dropped down

**Powerpoint crashed – so
lost screendumps from
P15 end to P17**

End R4.2 start P15 up to FL100

P17 end 500ft R5.1start

End R5.1 start P18

End P18 1800ft - too high

R5.2 start at 1500ft

Flight B410 13:21:52
 Heading 87 deg Speed 212 knots Height 1.3kft Press 964mb
 Lat 19°42.0'S Long 76°24.0'W Wind 11 ms-1/ 127 deg
 Temp 12.51C Dewpoint 8.2C
 From 12:41:32 to now

Current values
 ++++ STATIC PRESSURE 964.05 mb
 DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP 12.52 deg C
 ++++ DEW POINT 8.2 deg C

New plot, same times

Flight B410 13:24:41
 Heading 88 deg Speed 213 knots Height 1.3kft Press 963mb
 Lat 19°42.0'S Long 76°12.0'W Wind 10 ms-1/ 132 deg
 Temp 12.04C Dewpoint 9.52C
 From start to now

Current values
 — TIME FROM MIDNIGHT 48279 secs
 — JAW LIQUID WATER CONTENT 0.02 g m-3
 — NEVZOROV LIQUID WATER 0 g m-3

R5.2 end P19 start

CB 3500ft

**P19 end R5.3 started at 3800ft
bumpy - near CT - do
incloud run here to ensure in
cloud over RHB**

End R5.3, P20 start

CT 4900ft P20

P20 end, P21 start from 5900ft

P21 CT 4900ft

Start R5.4 incloud at 4300ft

Overhead R H Brown

End R5.4 P22 start

P22 CT 4700

End P22, start P23 at 5700ft

P23 CT at 4700ft

P23 CB about 2900ft

P23 end P24 start at 50ft

P24 end R6.1 start

P6.1 end at 500ft P25 start to 2900ft

End P25, start R6.2 at 2900 R6.2 2900ft below CB but in Cu base

End R6.2 at 2900 start P26

In cloud on P26

R6.3 at 3800ft (dropped down from 4300 at CT)

Turn at alpha R6.3

End R6.3 P27 start

P27 CT 4200ft

P27 end P28 start 5200ft

CT 4200ft P28

CB 3600ft P28

P28 end P29 start at 50ft

P29 end/R7.1 start 500ft

R7.1 end at 500ft P30start

P30 CB

R7.2 in cloud dropped 100 to 3600ft

Out of CT

Mission Scientist's Log

MISS SCI. 2

Flight No B...410 Date 29/10/08 Name Phil Brown Page 1 of 3

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
1057					CCN only 5cm ⁻³ but VACE reports Sulphate but low sea salt.
1058					Drizzle, peaks only 7-10L ⁻¹
105936					3000ft cloud base.
110001		3500			Run 2-3 2DC ~ 30-50L ⁻¹
1105		"			2DC - 70L ⁻¹ CDP - 150-200, MF 120-150 17µm 14
110915					LWC dropped along with drizzle
112230					ReAP ~ 40 CN ~ 200
112745					Lower SO ₄ ,
1129					Cloud 'ledge' ahead on video. Drizzle was absent in r-3.1 @ 500ft
		2000			on r-3.2, 2DC peaks ~ 10L ⁻¹
114420					Drizzle 10-20L ⁻¹ 6-800µm max. Just above cloud base at end of run.
		3500			V. variable cloud base, signs of lower Cu formation.
		3000			on 3-3. 2DC 20-50L ⁻¹
115736		111			~ 1/8 Cu below the Sc base
		4900			cloud top.
1211		500			Coming under clear areas.
1216					280 CN, 20 @ 0.6% CCN.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B. 410 Date 29/10/08 Name Page 2 of 3

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
122311		3000			Run 4.2 50 PCASP
122611					in turn at W point.
					low CCN @ 0.6% CAS 4 cm ⁻³
—			71° 56'		west point. v thin Sc layer above - more extensive to the N.
123313		//			Profile to F100 or above.
					19 3 .185 74 46.80 W RHB 35° @ DART base
—					1362 eta RHB.
125539					into cloud on profile ↘
—					open Cu penetrations visible.
					CCN was no good tower.
130159					Still decoupled Bk cloud base
130159	↘	500			Run 5.1 in last profile down P16
131146					Drizzle patches reaching SK ₀
		1500			on P5.2, 2DC ~ 50' peaks.
1327			76. W		still Cu below the Sc base.
132807		3900	75 48 W		P5.3 start. 2DC up to 100 L ⁻¹ but Dmax 150µm.
1335					2DC 50-1000' 300µm max.
—					CDP 70 cm ⁻³ MFSSP 50 cm ⁻³ 18µm 13µm
					CCN 30 cm ⁻³ @ 0.1% out of 200
133811					end 5.3
		4800			cloud top

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B** B410 Date 29/10/08 Name P. BARRETT Page 1 of 7

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
09.52					TAXI
10.00					T/O
10.02					cloud base ~ 2.3 kft cloud top = 3.5 kft
013943	P1				
	P2				- Negh profile - layers at different altitudes on descent profile
					cloud top = 4.3 kft cloud base = 3.3 kft
R1	(P3 - upto Soft)				HLW spike @ 0.2 gm ³ 4 minutes to reach Point X PCASP ~ 200 cm ⁻³
R2.1	10335L			AMS	sulphate - all mode ~ 3000 Point X CPC (CNC mode) ~ 550 cm ⁻³ PCASP ~ 28 cm ⁻³ base cloud all in aerosol mode CAD = 7 cm ⁻³ > 6µm nothing above 3µm wind similar to previous days.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B410**..... Date **29/10/08**.. Name **P. BARRETT** Page **2** of **7**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
10.43					CPL concs have fallen off as we move away from the coast ~500 → 300 cm ³
10.45					sub cloud for CU zero.
10.46	R22				CU 1 zero cloud at 3000 end at 2500 2.7kft - lots of turbulence a drizzle - cloud drooping?? 300ft below cloud some drizzle below cloud 20 - not much - can't detect on SW - may be giving the CU problems with a zero. - Cloud Base 3.0kft
10.50:01	R23		3.4		AMS - high messe - is it real? or is it oil, guessement Drizzle - light on windows COP - 150 - 200 $\rho = 17 \mu\text{m}$ FSP (M) 125 - 150 $\rho = 14, 15 \mu\text{m}$ CA3 - 13 - 15 μm 300 - 350 cm ³ LWC = 0.8 gm ⁻³

HWC $\approx 0.34 \text{ gm}^{-3}$

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B**..... Date Name Page 3 of 7

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					CLOUD TOP ~ 4.6
					CLOUD BASE ~ 3.1
					Drizzle below cloud
11.19.01	P 7	Soft			BIG drizzle drops 7800 μm ? -core cloud
					LDS $\rightarrow$
	R3.1				Soft above sea level
11.28					Dip, drizzle leading to show increases. Drizzle in lots of places.
1132.0	P9				climb to sub cloud run. variable cloud base.
113417	3.2				sub cloud run 100 cm^{-3} Drizzle: prodots - coarse on
					OW, New,
	1142				cloud base dropping
					Some drizzle above sub cloud
					across on Neph.
	1144				Big drizzle drops
	1144				in cloud
	P10				climb "into" cloud
114707	3.3	3.744			into CUI mode
					near cloud base
	11.52				near cloud base

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B...410**... Date **29/10/06**... Name **P. BARRETT**... Page **4**... of **7**...

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
11:33	1				- hole in cloud, strong turbulence
					- Down draught??
	(11.52)				AMS - high mass organics, sulphate.
					COP 50 - 150 cm ⁻³
	P11				big increase in LWC with height
	up to point and back down				Cloud top 4.9 kft
					Lds of Ci, 3/8 above
					cloud top 4.7 kft.
					cloud base 3.8 kft.
					↳ variable.
					De coupled - temperature
					→ Cumulus below Sc aerosol layer
12:07.42	R4.1	Soft			inhomogeneous cloud above.
12:11					Break in Cloud
					RASS ~ 55 cm ⁻³
					280 CN counts total
					CCN (max) = 20 at 0.69, 5 percent
12.1600					- increase in turbulence
12:18	P'				end R4.1
					climbing to a run at the same level as last cloud run
					- we will be in cloud free region

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B40** Date 29/10/08 Name P. BARRETT Page 5 of 7

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
12:23:11	R42	3.0kt			popped above inversion, it is lower than previous only 10% activated fraction CN at 0.6% spr sat in the cloud free region - only "UN-activatable" particles are left?? Similar to C130 results in P 04
					Decoupled - change in stability at ~ 450 hPa
12:35:13	Profile to 10kt	and back			dry above
			35kt		Rondeau is at 19° 38' 48.5" 74° 46' 50.4" W CCN inh has been closed for the outbound leg.

56'

Mission Scientist's LogFlight No **B.410**... Date **29/06/08**... Name **P. BARRATT**... Page **6** of **7**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
125557					cloud top = 4.6kft cloud base = 3.9kft
R.					
130255	S.1	800ft	W		Cu below Sz. Drizzle - 2D
13:13:34	S.2	1.3kft	WNW		TOTAL WATER (NEUT) seems to pick up drizzle better than other LWC probes
1317					large drizzle 2D, Neut
1323	P19				drizzle
13:20:	R53	3.6kft			in cloud top, lumpy 3.6kft patchy cloud peak 0.6 g m^{-3} small drizzle - 2D $\sim 80 \text{ cm}^{-3}$
1322					LWC ↑ larger Drizzle fsp(m) 50 cm^{-3} 13µm ODP 70 cm^{-3} 18µm ZDC 100 cm^{-3} updrafts and high LWC - 3 ocean 13:28 13:33 13:36 C/S $\sim 250 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ 1-2µm to cloud top, cloud top 4.7kft - in cloud over Ron Brown Higher LWC than at 3.6kft.
13:38:10	P20				
13:42:12	S4	4.3kft			

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B40**... Date **29/10/08**... Name **P. BARRETT** Page **7** of **7**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1352				4.4	cloud top = 3.7 kft
1354.18	P23	5.5 → 5.0			cloud base ~ 2.8 kft
					CU h ₀ = 60/300
					Cf 30/400 at furthest West
14:02:07	r6.1	500ft			looks like full cloud cover above
14.16.10	6.2	2.9 kft			Drizzle, ~10 cm ³ small
					↳ No - very clear signal
					↳ Tw - in the noise
14.18					FSSP - in cloud increases
14.19					sudden unexplained decrease?!
14.19					- SW above the noise
					Some small Cu
14.24					- hit cloud
14.28.28	r6.3	3.8			cloud top ~ 4.0 kft.
					lower LWC than previous were
					Westerly cloud top increases
					FSSP = 150 13 μm
					CPP = 200 17 μm
					ZWC 60 e ⁻¹
					through cloud top - CPP
					CAS = 380-400 Bpr LWC ~ 0.3
					CU LWC ~ 0.18
14.30					spike in LWC
14.34.54					turn back to ARCA at Point X
					mid run.

r7.2 - cloud top - popping cloud thinning at top.

VOCALS BAe-146 Instrument status Report

Date of report(UTC): 2008/10/29 17:00

Author of report: Keith Bower

Submitted at(UTC): 2008/10/30 21:08

Remaining flight hours: 50

General Comments:

After mission on 29/10/2008

INSTRUMENTS / SYSTEMS STATUS

 = no report

Meteorology / Navigation

1.	GPS (Patch)	Comment:	
2.	GPS (Cruciform)	Comment:	
3.	Temperature/Pressure	Comment:	
4.	Water Vapor (Hygrometer)	Comment:	
5.	Turbulence Probe	Comment:	
6.	Altitude (RadarAlt)	Comment:	
7.	Doppler Radar	Comment:	
8.	Dropsonde (AVAPS)	Comment:	

Radiation

9.	Broadband Radiometer (BBR)	Comment:	
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10.	Spectral Radiometer (ARIES)	Comment:
11.	In-flight Microwave Obs System (DEIMOS)	Comment:
12.	Microwave Radiometer Scanning System (MARSS)	Comment:
13.	Shortwave Spectrometer (SWS)	Comment:
14.	Spectral Irradiance (SHIM)	Comment: lower SHIMS not working
15.	Heimann Downward-facing Radiometer	Comment:

Chemistry

16.	Ozone (CAMP 2B)	Comment:
17.	NO _x	Comment:
18.	CO (AL5002)	Comment:
19.	SO ₂ (TECO 43C)	Comment:
20.	Sample Bottles (WAS)	Comment:
21.	CH ₄ /CO ₂ (NIR-TDLAS)	Comment:
22.	PAN (GC)	Comment: not operated
23.	Volatile Aerosol Composition (VACC)	Comment:
24.	CH ₄ /N ₂ O (1C-TDLAS)	Comment:

Cloud Physics and Aerosol

25.	Liquid and Total water probe	Comment:	
26.	LWC (Johnson Williams)	Comment:	
27.	TWC	Comment:	
28.	FFSSP	Comment:	
29.	2D-C	Comment:	
30.	PCASP	Comment:	possible slight noise in ch 1
31.	Small Ice Detector (SID-2)	Comment:	not fitted
32.	Cloud and Precipitation Imager (CIP-15)	Comment:	needs alignment
33.	Cloud Droplet Probe (CDP)	Comment:	
34.	Condensation Nucleus Counter (CNC)	Comment:	
35.	Cloud Condensation Nuclei Spectrometer (CCNc)	Comment:	leak from cabin during outbound part
36.	Fluorescence water vapour sensor (FWVS)	Comment:	
37.	Dry Nephelometer	Comment:	
38.	Wet Nephelometer	Comment:	brief period of lost data
39.	Black Carbon (PSAP)	Comment:	
40.	Filters	Comment:	probable contamination from inlet
41.	Aerosol Mass Spectrometer (AMS)	Comment:	
42.	Counter-flow virtual Impactor (CVI)	Comment:	zero cals below cloud may be affected by drizzle

43.	2-D Imaging Probe (SPEC-2D-S-128H)	Comment:	
44.	CAPS	Comment:	
45.	Single Particle Soot Photometer (SP-2)	Comment:	was not optimised
46.	Fine-mode Aerosol Spectrometer (UHSAS)	Comment:	not fitted
47.	Scanning Mobility Particle Sizer (SMPS)	Comment:	
48.	Ultrafine particle counter 1 (LP-WUCPC-1)	Comment:	
49.	Ultrafine particle counter 2 (LP-WUCPC-2)	Comment:	

Other

50.	SATCOM C	Comment:	
51.	SATCOM H	Comment:	
52.	Up, Down, Front, Rear Digital Imagery	Comment:	

[prev](#) | [next](#)

 [Back to VOCALS Field Catalog](#) | [edit](#) | [delete](#)

comments : gstoss at ucar.edu

Chemistry Log

Date: 29 Oct 2008

Flight: B410

Operator:

Doug Anderson

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Preflight

No.	? or x	Location	Action	Comments
<u>Gases</u>				
1	X	CO ₂ / Ar	Outlet pressure is between 2 and 2.5 bar	
2	X	CO ₂ / Ar	Inlet pressure not less than 20 psi	180 / 185
3	X	Nitrogen	Outlet pressure is between 2 and 2.5 bar	
4	X	Nitrogen	Inlet pressure not less than 20 psi, note pressure	48 / 48
5	X	CO standard	Outlet pressure is between 2 and 2.5 bar	
6	X	CO standard	Inlet pressure not less than 20 psi, note pressure	39 / 29 CO time synch check @ 08:12:55
<u>Flows</u>				
7	X	Ozone sample flows	Flow ~ 07. LPM on both channels	
8	X	NOx sample flow	~ 1 LPM	
9	X	NOx Ozonator flow	~ 0.065 LPM	
10	X	CO lamp flow	~ 40 ml/min	
11	X	CO pressure cell	~ 7.5 bar	
12	X	CO pressure monochromator	~ 5 bar	
<u>Zeros</u>				
13	X	Ozone zero	Performed OK (if not approx zero note values)	
14	X	NOx zero	Performed OK (if not approx zero note values)	
15	X	CO zero	Left for approx 10 min	08:41:45 to 09:55:00
16	X	SO ₂ zero (not for most flights)	Left for approx 10 min	.48 lpm
<u>Other</u>				
17	X	Tubing	All inlets / exhausts connected	
18	X	HORACE data	Check data is being displayed and recorded	
19	No	CO calibration	If unattended set to auto cal (40 min)	
<u>TDLAS</u>				
20	n/a	230V	230V power breakers on	
21	n/a	28V	Red LED on front panel (ensure LTI breaker on)	
22	n/a	Laptop	On and software working	
23	n/a	Data	Being saved to correct directories	

Post flight

<u>Switch Off</u>				
1	X	CO	Switch off instrument	
2	X	Ozone	Switch off monitor	
3	X	NOx	Switch off monitor	
4	X	Pumps	Switch off all pumps	
5	X	Breaker	Pop all breakers on rack and SSP	
<u>Gases (note pressures)</u>				
6	X	CO ₂ /Ar	Close valves and check inlet pressure not below 20 psi	See above for final value
7	X	CO standard	Close valves and check inlet pressure not below 20 psi	See above for final value
8	X	Nitrogen	Close valves and check inlet pressure not below 20 psi If below 20 psi then the cylinder needs changing refilling	See above for final value
<u>Driers</u>				
9	X	Small drier	Change if spent	
10	X	Large drier	Change if spent	
<u>TDLAS</u>				
11	n/a	Data transfer	To memory stick	
12	n/a	Laptop	Shut down	
13	n/a	Switch off instrument	Pull all breakers IF no other instrument on	
<u>Log</u>				
14	X	Flight Log	Put log in folder (notify Ruth of any issues)	
15	None	Faults	Fill out separate log for in flight issues put in flight folder	
16	n/a	TDLAS data	Send to project spaces on BADC	

Chemistry Log

Date: 29 Oct 2008

Flight: B410

Operator:

Doug Anderson

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In flight

CO calibrations only need carrying out when the lamp temperature changes, if unsure perform a quick cal first. During each CO calibration check Ozone and NOx flows are similar to those observed pre-flight

Time	Flight level	CO Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	CO Bkgrd (ppbV)	CO Bkgrd Count (Hz)	CO Cell Pressure (Torr)	CO Lamp Temp (deg C)
27/10/08 19:55:25	Previous flight for ref.	88.59	339.73	30096.27	-	-
Time	Flight level	CO Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	CO Bkgrd (ppbV)	CO Bkgrd Count (Hz)	CO Cell Pressure (Torr)	CO Lamp Temp (deg C)
09:34:32	Ground, pre power c/o	92.26	331.01	30363.60	39.98	7.52
Time	Flight level	CO Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	CO Bkgrd (ppbV)	CO Bkgrd Count (Hz)	CO Cell Pressure (Torr)	CO Lamp Temp (deg C)
09:41:03	Ground, pre power c/o	91.58	329.12	30315.17	39.79	7.52
Time	Flight level	CO Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	CO Bkgrd (ppbV)	CO Bkgrd Count (Hz)	CO Cell Pressure (Torr)	CO Lamp Temp (deg C)
09:56:37	Ground, during taxi	92.08	326.12	30028.83	40.23	7.50
Time	Flight level	CO Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	CO Bkgrd (ppbV)	CO Bkgrd Count (Hz)	CO Cell Pressure (Torr)	CO Lamp Temp (deg C)

Flight level	Zero Start time	Zero End time	Counts (Hz)	Span Start time	Span End time	Conc. Range	Counts range	Pressure Cell (Torr)	Lamp Temp	O3 Intensities
500'	10:30:35	10:31:20	29635 -30060	10:31:35	10:32:15	503-519		92.08	326.12	30028.83
500'	11:21:24	11:22:16	29165-30115	11:22:24	11:24:19	504-517	76922 - 77765	92.08	326.12	30028.83
500'	12:07:54	12:09:06	29386 - 30115	12:09:11	12:09:59		77665 - 78491			
500'	13:02:20	13:03:10	29237 - 30011	13:03:13	13:04:26	515-533	77486 - 78744			
4100'	13:49:40	13:50:33	28974 -29538	13:50:45	13:51:30		7713478581			
3600'	14:30:16	14:31:00	28nnn - 29550	14:31:08	14:31:58	511-528	77019278572			
Ground taxi	15:17:06	15:17:50	29176 29590	15:17:52	15:18:45	516-536	77616 78259			
Ground taxi Normal cal	15:2									
Ground, post power changeover	16:52:00	16:53:00	26662 - 27103	16:53:02	16:54:003	489 - 503	72202 - 72555	7.50	40.53	A: 103507 B: 123968

Time	Flight level	CO Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	CO Bkgrd (ppbV)	CO Bkgrd Count (Hz)	CO Cell Pressure (Torr)	CO Lamp Temp (deg C)
Time	Flight level	CO Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	CO Bkgrd (ppbV)	CO Bkgrd Count (Hz)	CO Cell Pressure (Torr)	CO Lamp Temp (deg C)
Time	Flight level	CO Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	CO Bkgrd (ppbV)	CO Bkgrd Count (Hz)	CO Cell Pressure (Torr)	CO Lamp Temp (deg C)

In flight comments

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 410

Date: 29/10/08	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 08:10:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 1 of 5
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		Manchester FSSP		CIP25			CDP			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Mean Dia	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Mean Dia	LWC		
10:02:56	160	0.28	234			8	100	300	12				300	18	0.6	12	FL030
10:04:20	90	0.08	272														FL040
10:04:53	75	0.08															FL050
10:06:09	60	0.08															FL060
10:06:58	45	0.09															FL070
10:08:06	85	0.10															FL080
10:09:02	40	0.08															FL090
10:10:15	35	0.08															End of Profile 1 @ FL100
10:18:03	30	0.08															Start Profile 2 from FL100
10:19:05	45	0.08															FL090
10:19:57	55	0.09															FL080
10:20:52	25	0.08															FL070
10:21:51	25	0.07															FL060
10:22:47	45	0.09															FL050
10:23:49	220	0.22	341			4	75	220	15				190	15	0.3	12	FL040
10:24:58	200	0.09	386														FL030
10:26:17	210	0.09	387														FL020
10:27:20	220	0.09															FL010
10:29:28	250	0.08															End of Profile 1 & Start Profile 2@ 50'
10:30:17																	End of Profile2 & Start Run 1@ 500'
10:31:00	215	0.08															
10:33:00	200	0.08															
10:33:55																	End of Run 1 & Start Run 2.1 @ 500'
10:34:00	190	0.09															
10:36:00	190	0.08															
10:38:00	145	0.09															
10:40:00	145	0.08	408														
10:42:00	120	0.08															
10:44:53																	End of Run 2.1& Start P3
10:45:40	130	0.08															FL010
10:46:31	110	0.08															FL020
10:47:15																	End of Profile 3 @ 3000'
10:48:19																	Start Run 2.2 @ 2500'
10:49:00	140	0.09	422														
10:51:00	110	0.09	442														
10:53:00	110	0.09	445			3	200									12	
10:55:00	100	0.09				2	300									12	
10:57:00	100	0.09	446			2	300									12	
10:59:00																	End of Run & Start P 5
11:00:01																	End of P5 & Start Run 2.3 @ 3500'
11:01:00	280	0.31	648			30	250	100	11			0.3	200	17	0.35	1	
11:03:00	300	0.34	894			20	300	100	12			0.6	200	20	0.6	1	
11:05:00	300	0.38	1178			45	150	100	13			0.4	150	18	0.4	1	

PCASP Reference Volts = 7.7V	FFSSP Reference Volts = 3.4V	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -1.4V	CIP25 End element 1 voltage = 0.7V	CIP100 End element 1 voltage = n/a
PCASP Flow rate = 1.6 cc/sec		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -1.4V	CIP25 End element 64 voltage = 0.6V	CIP100 End element 64 voltage = n/a
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = n/a	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = n/a		

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Date: 29/10/08	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 08:10:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 2 of 5
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		Manchester FSSP		CIP25			CDP			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Mean Dia	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Mean Dia	LWC		
11:07:00	150	0.25	1421			25	200	120	14			0.4	180	17	0.4	1	
11:09:00	90	0.17	1652			9	200	140	14			0.4	160	17	0.35	1	
11:10:51																	End of Run 2.3 & Start Profile 6
11:11:29	890	0.38	2011			60	200	150	20			0.8	150	23	1.1	1	FL040
11:13:06	35	0.07															End of P6 & Start P7 @ FL056
11:13:25	30	0.07	2043														FL050
11:14:25	275	0.35	2118			40	200	100	18			0.8	100	23	0.8	1	FL040
11:15:30	60	0.10	2195			10	200										FL030
11:16:42	75	0.08	2196			1	300									1	FL020
11:17:52	70	0.08				1	700									1	FL010
11:20:35	40	0.08															End of Profile 7 & Start Profile 8 @ 50'
11:21:22																	End of Profile 8 & Start Run 3.1 @ 500'
11:22:00	45	0.08	2197														
11:24:00	70	0.09															
11:26:00	55	0.09															
11:28:00	60	0.09	2198														
11:30:00	65	0.09															
11:32:08																	End of Run 3.1 & Start P9
11:33:10	55	0.08	2199			1											FL010
11:34:17																	End of P9 & Start Run 3.2 @ 2600'
11:35:00	60	0.08	2200			1											
11:37:00	50	0.09	2201			1	250									1	
11:39:00	50	0.10	2202			2	300									1	
11:41:00	60	0.08															
11:43:00	55	0.09	2203			2	300									1	
11:45:14																	End of Run & Start P10
11:47:06																	End of P10 & Start Run 3.3 @ 3900'
11:48:00	150	0.30	2438			30	200	100	12			0.3	100	18	0.3	1	
11:50:00	440	0.31	2651			15	250	100	14			0.35	100	17	0.2	1	
11:52:00	90	0.26	2900			6	150	100	13			0.25	140	17	0.25	1	
11:54:00	55	0.14	3027			7	125	50	10			0.2	120	16	0.15	1	
11:56:00	35	0.13	3124			4	100	100	10			0.2	70	15	0.2	12	
11:57:55																	End of Run 3.3 & Start Profile 11
12:00:04	15	0.09	3277														End of Profile 11 & Start P12 @ 5900'
12:01:03	20	0.08															FL050
12:01:59	65	0.19	3360														FL040
12:02:59	70	0.08															FL030
12:03:55	55	0.09	3361														FL020
12:04:55	80	0.08															FL010
12:07:11	70	0.08															End of P12 & Start P13 @ 50'
12:07:48																	End of P13 & Start Run 4.1 @500'
12:08:00	70	0.09	3362														
12:10:00	65	0.08															

PCASP Reference Volts = 7.7V	FFSSP Reference Volts = 3.4V	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -1.4V	CIP25 End element 1 voltage = 0.7V	CIP100 End element 1 voltage = n/a
PCASP Flow rate = 1.6 cc/sec		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -1.4V	CIP25 End element 64 voltage = 0.6V	CIP100 End element 64 voltage = n/a
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = n/a	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = n/a		

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 410

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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		Manchester FSSP		CIP25			CDP			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Mean Dia	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Mean Dia	LWC		
12:12:00	70	0.08	3363														
12:14:00	75	0.08	3364														
12:16:00	60	0.08															
12:18:33																End of Run 4.1 & Start P14	
12:19:18	40	0.09	3366													FL010	
12:20:19	50	0.09														FL020	
12:21:53	40	0.08														End of P14 @ 3900'	
12:23:16																Start Run 4.3 @ 500'	
12:24:00	40	0.08	3527														
12:26:00	40	0.08	3635														
12:28:00	40	0.08															
12:30:00	35	0.08															
12:32:00	35	0.08	3636														
12:33:14																End of Run & Start P15	
12:33:30	35	0.08														FL030	
12:34:25	40	0.09														FL040	
12:35:20	25	0.08														FL050	
12:43:35	5	0.09														FL120	
12:44:50	5	0.08														FL130	
12:45:48	5	0.07	3659													FL140	
12:46:16																End of P15 & Start P16 @ FL145	
12:47:47	8	0.08	3883													FL130	
12:48:35	4	0.09														FL120	
12:49:33	7	0.08														FL110	
12:50:31	14	0.08														FL100	
12:51:19	15	0.08														FL090	
12:52:14	10	0.08														FL080	
12:53:23	15	0.08														FL070	
12:54:17	15	0.08														FL060	
12:55:15	25	0.08														FL050	
12:56:17	80	0.13	3901													FL040	
12:57:16	65	0.08	3945													FL030	
12:58:14	60	0.08														FL020	
12:59:17	60	0.08	3946													FL010	
13:01:20	35	0.08														End of Profile 16 & Start P17 @ 50'	
13:01:58																End of P17 & Start Run 5.1 @ 500'	
13:02:00	70	0.08															
13:04:00	70	0.08															
13:06:00	55	0.08															
13:08:00	60	0.08															
13:10:00	60	0.08															
13:12:57																End of Run 5.1 & Start P18	
13:13:44	50	0.08														FL010	

PCASP Reference Volts = 7.7V	FFSSP Reference Volts = 3.4V	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -1.4V	CIP25 End element 1 voltage = 0.7V	CIP100 End element 1 voltage = n/a
PCASP Flow rate = 1.6 cc/sec		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -1.4V	CIP25 End element 64 voltage = 0.6V	CIP100 End element 64 voltage = n/a
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = n/a	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = n/a		

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 410

Date: 29/10/08	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 08:10:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 4 of 5
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		Manchester FSSP		CIP25			CDP			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Mean Dia	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Mean Dia	LWC		
13:14:35																End of P18 & Start Run 5.2 @ 1500'	
13:15:00	55	0.08	3948														
13:17:00	55	0.09	3949			3	700								1		
13:19:00	50	0.09				1											
13:21:00	40	0.09	3950														
13:23:00	50	0.08															
13:25:00	40	0.10				2	450								1		
13:25:34																End of Run 5.2 & Start P19	
13:28:08																End of P19 & Start Run 5.3 @ 3900	
13:29:00	190	0.32	4072			110	200	50	12			0.2	70	20	0.2	1	
13:31:00	50	0.22	4123			60	275	50	10			0.3	80	20	0.15	1	
13:33:00	50	0.22	4276			60	200	50	13			0.3	70	18	0.1	1	
13:35:00	150	0.41	4371			100	300	60	18			0.6	100	21	0.6	1	
13:37:00	360	0.43	4559			50	475	60	18			0.5	100	21	0.6	1	
13:38:09																End of Run & Start P20	
13:40:31	20	0.08	4715													End of P20 & Start P21 @ FL055	
13:41:33	30	0.09														FL050	
13:42:12																End of P21 & Start Run 5.4 @4300'	
13:43:00	230	0.39	4872			70	275	70	20			0.6	100	12	0.2	1	
13:45:00	650	0.42	5334			130	300	80	20			0.7	150	12	0.2	1	
13:47:00	615	0.44	5644			140	300	75	20			0.6	150	20	0.4	1	
13:49:00	540	0.44	5893			54	200	100	19			0.8	150	21	0.8	1	
13:51:00	700	0.44	6067			100	225	100	19			0.8	140	22	0.75	1	
13:52:36																End of Run 5.4 & Start P22	
13:54:09	20	0.06	6220													End of P22 & Start P23 @ 5700'	
13:54:55	25	0.07														FL050	
13:55:52	240	0.38	6345			50	200	100	17						1	FL040	
13:57:57	70	0.08	6417													FL020	
13:59:05	75	0.08														FL010	
14:02:17	70	0.08														End of Profile 23 & Start Profile 24 @ 50'	
14:02:49	80	0.08														End of P24 & Start Run 6.1 @ 500'	
14:03:00	80	0.08															
14:05:00	100	0.09	6418			1	200										
14:07:00	110	0.08															
14:09:00	120	0.08															
14:11:00	135	0.08															
14:13:40																End of Run & Start P25	
14:14:33	100	0.08														FL010	
14:15:27	120	0.08	6419													FL020	
14:16:10																End of P25 & Start Run 6.2 @ 2900'	
14:17:00	120	0.09	6420			1	200										
14:19:00	100	0.14	6433			4	200										
14:21:00	90	0.09	6437														

PCASP Reference Volts = 7.7V	FFSSP Reference Volts = 3.4V	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -1.4V	CIP25 End element 1 voltage = 0.7V	CIP100 End element 1 voltage = n/a
PCASP Flow rate = 1.6 cc/sec		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -1.4V	CIP25 End element 64 voltage = 0.6V	CIP100 End element 64 voltage = n/a
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = n/a	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = n/a		

Size	#	Charged	Flight/Date	Discharged
10 1	2 1 } 1	27/10	B410/29/10 (KMG)	MC 30/10
10 1	8 7 } 1	27/10	B410/29/10	MC 3/10
10 1	3 4 } 1	28/10	B410/29/10	MC 30/10
10 1	21 23 } 1	28/10	B410/29/10	MC 30/10
10 1	33 40 } 1	28/10	B410/29/10	MC 30/10
10 1	10 69 } 1	28/10	B410/29/10	MC 30/10

Filter No .LOC TON TOPF RUN Acc Vol Total Vol

CVI log

10/29/08 8:46:00 AM
10/29/08 8:50:50 AM
10/29/08 9:23:42 AM
10/29/08 9:32:57 AM preflight probs: aparent ca
10/29/08 9:33:08 AM preflight probs: aparent ca
10/29/08 9:38:55 AM test at begining - lyman - counterflow to zero - get one reading
- swap over get a higher reading.
10/29/08 9:39:02 AM shouldn't they be the same/
10/29/08 9:41:57 AM shouldn't they be the same/
10/29/08 9:42:00 AM shouldn't they be the same/
10/29/08 10:08:58 AM shouldn't they be the same/
10/29/08 10:10:09 AM All zero with low counter flow cntl (2) on high transit, there
for no cabin leaks??
10/29/08 10:13:33 AM cf to 1 cf valve closed, aerosol mode
10/29/08 10:14:26 AM cf to 1 cf valve closed, aerosol mode
10/29/08 10:14:36 AM cf to 1 cf valve closed, aerosol mode
10/29/08 10:14:41 AM cf to 1 cf valve closed, aerosol mode
10/29/08 10:16:21 AM cf to 1 cf valve closed, aerosol mode
10/29/08 10:23:34 AM cloud cf on
10/29/08 10:25:09 AM cf off, aerosol mode
10/29/08 10:41:43 AM PCASP generally agreeing with cloud physics
10/29/08 10:44:53 AM cf mode ready for cal
10/29/08 10:45:16 AM cf mode ready for cal
10/29/08 10:45:28 AM cf mode ready for cal
10/29/08 10:45:37 AM cf mode ready for cal
10/29/08 10:46:16 AM cf at 3.8, dials set 0.72 and 0,6
10/29/08 10:47:34 AM cf at 3.8, dials set 0.72 and 0,6
10/29/08 10:47:43 AM droppinf, in cloud
10/29/08 10:49:04 AM more cloud,
10/29/08 10:56:05 AM CF of 6 to get flat line, ish
10/29/08 10:56:18 AM hygro to zero.
10/29/08 10:58:55 AM hygro to zero.
10/29/08 10:59:26 AM drizzle reported, cf back 4& go for cloud
10/29/08 10:59:52 AM drizzle reported, cf back 4& go for cloud
10/29/08 10:59:57 AM in cloud
10/29/08 11:00:55 AM hygo back to sample
10/29/08 11:01:15 AM AMS seeing lots of high masses.
10/29/08 11:10:48 AM manchester reporting 0.3 to 0.5 water content.
10/29/08 11:11:23 AM climbing above cloud, leave in cf mode to check zero
10/29/08 11:12:01 AM cloud break
10/29/08 11:13:48 AM Manchester to rosemount momentary, back down to cloud.
10/29/08 11:14:05 AM Manchester to rosemount momentary, back down to cloud.
10/29/08 11:14:13 AM in cloud
10/29/08 11:15:36 AM cloud base: now 3.1k
10/29/08 11:16:43 AM AMS were seeing distribution peak at 10's of nanometers, small
leak to cabin, maybe on interack pipe.
10/29/08 11:17:49 AM zero not comin below cloud. maybe drissle again?
10/29/08 11:18:45 AM rain, on front screen
10/29/08 11:20:02 AM leave cf mode.
10/29/08 11:21:16 AM aerosol mode
10/29/08 11:22:14 AM zero bit poor down to 50ft. got much better lower we got.
10/29/08 11:22:48 AM cloud physics reporting large drizzle droplets below cloud.
10/29/08 11:28:51 AM drizzle
10/29/08 11:34:05 AM climbing for just blow cloud base run, cloud base varialbe
10/29/08 11:35:46 AM PCSP counts much higher here, this is why cannot zero below
cloud.
10/29/08 11:39:20 AM drizzle seen occasionally
10/29/08 11:43:20 AM drizzle or cloud base.
10/29/08 11:44:01 AM CF mode
10/29/08 11:44:08 AM CF mode
10/29/08 11:44:12 AM CF mode
10/29/08 11:44:27 AM lots of drizzle
10/29/08 11:45:54 AM manchester to CVI
10/29/08 11:46:27 AM no zero beforecloud due to drizzle.
10/29/08 11:46:52 AM patchy cloud.
10/29/08 11:47:14 AM in cloud run
10/29/08 11:52:34 AM cloud thin and patchy

10/29/08 11:53:17 AM AMS seeing 20nm peak, high masses and sulphates
10/29/08 11:53:43 AM clear spots
10/29/08 12:00:27 PM AMS on Rosemount dial to zero
10/29/08 12:00:47 PM AMS on Rosemount dial to zero
10/29/08 12:01:02 PM guess same for sp2.
10/29/08 12:01:58 PM cf to 3
10/29/08 12:02:07 PM cf to 3
10/29/08 12:02:40 PM out of cloud, variable cloud base.
10/29/08 12:03:01 PM out of cloud, variable cloud base.
10/29/08 12:05:21 PM aerosol mode
10/29/08 12:15:25 PM cloud physics gicing approx 55c/cc
10/29/08 12:18:49 PM climb to below patchy cloud run
10/29/08 12:21:30 PM pcasp flow tweaked
10/29/08 12:25:30 PM doing a below inversion run instead of below cloud. Not enough cloud.
10/29/08 12:27:41 PM core cloud pcasp seeing 40 per cc
10/29/08 12:32:18 PM profile to 10000, no cloud above so leave in aerosol mode.
10/29/08 12:55:34 PM cf on for cloud
10/29/08 12:55:40 PM cloud
10/29/08 12:59:29 PM cf off, aerosol mode
10/29/08 1:06:34 PM core cloud ages with pcasp 50-60c/cc
10/29/08 1:11:25 PM drizzle
10/29/08 1:15:35 PM below cloud run, big peaks, drizzle?
10/29/08 1:24:03 PM cf mode on for in cloud run
10/29/08 1:24:36 PM cf mode on for in cloud run
10/29/08 1:25:14 PM manchester flow set ready
10/29/08 1:27:38 PM cloud
10/29/08 1:28:06 PM maybe drizzle just before entering cloud
10/29/08 1:39:21 PM leave in cf mode above cloud, check zero.
10/29/08 1:41:45 PM ok zero above cloud
10/29/08 1:42:02 PM back in cloud
10/29/08 1:52:17 PM interesting saw tooth stucture on hygro
10/29/08 1:53:40 PM above cloud
10/29/08 1:54:55 PM reasonable zero, occasional particles <10
10/29/08 1:55:02 PM reasonable zero, occasional particles <10
10/29/08 1:55:22 PM cloud
10/29/08 1:58:41 PM manchester to rosemount
10/29/08 1:58:52 PM manchester to rosemount
10/29/08 1:59:07 PM cf off aerosol mode
10/29/08 2:05:16 PM manchester dials to zero, forgot earlier
10/29/08 2:16:32 PM drizzle
10/29/08 2:21:19 PM dropping to avoid cloud
10/29/08 2:21:35 PM back up...
10/29/08 2:21:52 PM cloud
10/29/08 2:22:34 PM ignore lasr cloud call
10/29/08 2:24:20 PM cloud
10/29/08 2:25:55 PM cf on ready for cloud run
10/29/08 2:26:11 PM cf on ready for cloud run
10/29/08 2:27:23 PM cloud
10/29/08 2:34:37 PM cloud thinning.
10/29/08 2:39:41 PM climb above cloud, check zero.
10/29/08 2:40:02 PM cloud free
10/29/08 2:42:01 PM ok zero just before cloud tops
10/29/08 2:42:07 PM cloud.
10/29/08 2:44:24 PM good zero now
10/29/08 2:45:27 PM cf off aerosol mode.
10/29/08 2:51:45 PM tweaked PCASP flows.
10/29/08 2:57:45 PM cf mode ready for profile to cloud run
10/29/08 2:59:54 PM patch cloud run
10/29/08 3:04:32 PM cf left on in manchester mode for landing.
10/29/08 3:23:04 PM hygro t valve to zero
10/29/08 3:26:02 PM hygro t valve to zero
10/29/08 3:26:39 PM PCASP zero easy when hygro switched to diluant??
10/29/08 3:26:46 PM All off

Wet Nephelometer Log

Flight No **B..410**

Date .29/10/08.

Operator's name D Tiddeman.....

Page .1..... of

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
10:15:20		10kft	10.0	10.3	37.4	10	20	dry neph on asr12,com2 chiller on
10:32:30	R1	500ft	13.5	46.1	37.4	45	10	
10:38:30	R2.1	500ft	13.6	47.8	81.7	10	42	
11:21:19	R3.1	500ft	13.6	41.9	43.2	45	10	
11:23 -11:30								Software died restarted
11:32:40	R3.1		13.0	41.9	73.8	5	45	
11:40:30	R3.2	2000ft	12.9	38	50.2	40	19	
11:45:43	R3.2	2000ft	12.6	41.9	71.3	10	39	
11:48								Chiller off
12:00:30			11.7	4.1	45.1			Chiller on
12:09:15	R4.1	500ft	13.5	44.5	44.2	40	13	
12:15:50	R4.1	500ft	13.4	41.9	73.4	10	39	
12:25:10	R4.2	3000ft	12.3	35.4	42.4	42	16	
12:34:30			11.6	31.8	75	5	42	
12:39:50								Chiller off
12:56:20								Chiller on
13:03:50	R5.1	500ft	13.4	42.5	40.1	42	14	
13:09:45	R5.1	500ft	13.3	51.3	80.6	7	42	
13:15:50	R5.2	1500ft	12.9	39.0	51.7	45	22	
13:22:50	R5.2	1500ft	12.8	37	83.1	6	43	
14:05:40	R6.1	500ft	13.3	39	37	45	7	
14:12:20	R6.1	500ft	13.3	39.3	82.3	7.5	45	

B410_SWS_SHIMS_EventLog.txt

```

05:13:12.36 --- - - - -
05:13:12.36 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
05:13:12.36 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
05:13:12.36 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B410
05:13:12.36 --- - - - -
05:13:15.24 SWS - - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
05:13:26.61 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
05:13:26.70 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
05:13:26.79 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
05:13:33.71 SWS - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
05:13:37.58 SWS - - 30 - - - - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 30ms.
05:13:37.59 SWS - - - 30 - - - - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 30ms.
05:13:40.39 USH - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
05:13:46.33 USH - - - 5 - - - - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
05:13:49.28 USH - - 30 - - - - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 30ms.
05:13:49.29 USH - - - 30 - - - - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 30ms.
05:13:51.76 LSH - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
05:13:53.50 LSH - - - 5 - - - - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
05:13:58.07 LSH - - 30 - - - - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 30ms.
05:13:58.08 LSH - - - 30 - - - - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 30ms.
05:14:05.98 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
05:14:05.98 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
05:14:05.98 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
05:14:09.86 SWS - - - - Idling
05:14:09.87 LSH - - - - Idling
05:14:09.88 USH - - - - Idling
05:14:15.71 --- - - - - *** 16 deg
05:14:33.21 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
05:15:14.73 SWS - - - - Telescope motor initialised.
05:15:16.80 SWS - - - - Telescope disabled.
05:15:33.01 SWS - - - - Telescope motor initialised.
05:15:40.15 SWS 0.0 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
05:15:58.31 SWS -6.0 - - - - Telescope sent to 100.000
05:15:59.42 SWS 99.9 - - - - Telescope stopped.
05:16:02.40 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
05:16:02.85 SWS - - - - Idling
05:16:06.56 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
05:16:06.56 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
05:16:06.57 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
05:16:14.63 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
05:16:19.47 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
05:16:19.53 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
05:16:19.56 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
05:16:20.20 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
05:16:20.40 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
05:16:20.66 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
05:16:22.28 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
05:16:22.28 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
05:16:22.34 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
05:16:23.03 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
05:16:23.23 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
05:16:23.46 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
05:16:29.69 SWS - - - - Idling
05:16:29.74 USH - - - - Idling
05:16:29.75 LSH - - - - Idling
05:16:29.78 LSH - - - - Idling
05:16:35.43 --- - - - - *** 15 deg
05:18:49.15 --- - - - - *** 14 deg
05:23:17.18 --- - - - - *** 13 deg
05:25:40.73 --- - - - - *** 12 deg
05:30:04.84 --- - - - - *** 11 deg
05:32:24.51 --- - - - - *** 12
05:40:30.84 --- - - - - *** 12 deg
05:40:36.51 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
05:40:36.52 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
05:40:36.53 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.

```

05:40:40.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
05:40:41.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
05:40:41.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
05:40:43.46	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
05:57:48.33	---	-	-	-	-	*** 11 deg
06:22:58.52	---	-	-	-	-	*** 10 deg
06:23:10.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:23:10.72	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:23:10.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:23:17.88	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
06:23:23.27	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
06:23:28.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:23:28.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:23:28.62	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:23:29.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:23:29.54	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:23:29.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:23:54.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:23:54.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:23:54.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:23:55.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:23:55.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:23:55.36	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:23:55.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
06:23:56.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
06:24:00.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:24:00.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:27:16.67	---	-	-	-	-	*** 10 degt
06:28:59.81	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
06:29:08.71	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
06:29:13.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:29:13.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:29:15.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:29:16.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:29:17.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:29:18.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:29:20.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:29:20.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:29:22.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:29:23.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:29:24.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:29:24.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:29:27.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:29:27.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:29:28.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:29:29.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:29:31.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:29:32.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:29:39.25	LSH	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 30ms to 50ms.
06:29:39.25	LSH	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 30ms to 50ms.
06:29:43.34	USH	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 30ms to 50ms.
06:29:43.34	USH	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 30ms to 50ms.
06:29:45.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:29:46.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:29:47.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:29:48.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:29:49.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:29:50.36	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:29:51.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:29:52.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:29:53.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:29:54.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:44:21.11	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
06:44:24.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:44:25.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:44:30.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:44:31.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
06:44:34.66	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:44:35.62	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

07:01:09.22	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 30ms to 100ms.
07:01:09.23	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 30ms to 100ms.
07:01:13.42	USH	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 100ms.
07:01:13.42	USH	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 100ms.
07:01:17.09	LSH	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 100ms.
07:01:17.10	LSH	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 100ms.
07:01:20.25	LSH	-	-	600	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 600ms.
07:01:20.26	LSH	-	-	-	600	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 600ms.
07:01:25.56	USH	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 200ms.
07:01:25.56	USH	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 200ms.
07:01:29.52	SWS	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 300ms.
07:01:29.53	SWS	-	-	-	300	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 300ms.
07:01:33.35	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 200ms.
07:01:33.36	SWS	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 200ms.
07:01:35.38	SWS	100.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
07:01:36.53	SWS	-5.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
07:01:40.35	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
07:01:45.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:01:48.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:01:49.55	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:01:51.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:01:53.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:01:59.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:02:06.17	---	-	-	-	-	*** 9 deg
07:05:40.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:05:42.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:05:42.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:05:45.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:05:45.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:05:51.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:08:07.47	---	-	-	-	-	*** 11 deg
07:09:05.45	USH	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 50ms.
07:09:05.46	USH	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 50ms.
07:09:07.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:09:08.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:09:12.58	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 50ms.
07:09:12.58	SWS	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 50ms.
07:09:13.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:09:14.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:09:16.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:09:17.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:09:19.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:09:25.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:09:41.82	---	-	-	-	-	*** 11 deg
07:11:38.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:11:39.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:11:41.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:11:42.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:11:45.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:11:47.88	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
07:11:51.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:12:39.86	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
07:12:57.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:12:58.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:12:59.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:13:00.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:14:09.24	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
07:16:09.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:16:10.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:16:10.74	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
07:16:12.43	SWS	171.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
07:16:27.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:16:28.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:17:11.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:17:12.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:17:12.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:17:13.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:17:15.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:17:21.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

07:17:45.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:17:46.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:17:47.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:17:48.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:20:26.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:20:26.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:20:28.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:20:29.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:20:30.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:20:37.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:23:59.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:24:00.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:24:01.33	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
07:24:03.06	SWS	-5.1	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
07:24:04.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:24:05.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:24:06.32	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:24:07.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:24:08.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:24:10.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:24:11.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:24:12.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:24:13.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:24:14.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:24:22.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:24:28.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:25:44.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:25:45.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:25:46.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:25:47.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:25:48.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:25:54.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:28:05.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:28:06.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:28:07.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:28:08.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:28:10.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:28:16.52	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:31:05.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:31:06.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:31:07.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:31:08.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:31:11.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:31:17.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:31:54.19	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
07:32:39.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:32:40.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:32:40.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:32:41.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:32:43.35	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:32:49.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:36:51.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:36:52.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:36:54.62	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:36:55.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:36:56.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:37:03.20	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:37:52.07	---	-	-	-	-	*** 11 deg
07:38:40.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:38:41.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:38:41.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:38:42.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:38:43.66	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:38:50.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:41:08.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:41:08.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:41:08.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:41:11.56	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
07:41:16.41	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000

07:41:18.12	SWS	173.3	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
07:41:19.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:41:19.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:41:19.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:41:24.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:41:25.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:41:26.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:41:27.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:41:28.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:41:35.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:41:49.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:41:49.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:41:49.05	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:41:49.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:41:50.84	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
07:41:52.53	SWS	-2.5	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
07:41:53.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:41:53.54	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:41:53.55	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:41:55.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:41:56.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:41:57.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:41:58.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:41:59.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:42:06.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:42:33.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:42:34.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:42:37.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:42:37.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:42:37.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:42:39.24	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
07:42:42.48	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
07:42:45.72	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:42:45.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:42:45.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:42:46.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:42:47.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:42:48.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:42:48.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:42:52.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:42:56.91	SWS	-	-	35	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 35ms.
07:42:56.92	SWS	-	-	-	35	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 35ms.
07:42:58.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:42:58.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:43:01.01	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 35ms to 75ms.
07:43:01.02	SWS	-	-	-	75	NIR int.time changed from 35ms to 75ms.
07:43:04.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:43:05.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:43:28.65	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
07:43:31.89	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
07:44:21.24	---	-	-	-	-	
07:44:21.24	---	-	-	-	-	+++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
07:44:21.24	---	-	-	-	-	+++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
						tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
07:44:21.24	---	-	-	-	-	+++ Flight no. B410
07:44:21.24	---	-	-	-	-	
07:44:32.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
07:44:32.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
07:44:32.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
07:44:35.87	SWS	-	-	-	5	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
07:44:38.57	SWS	-	-	45	-	VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 45ms.
07:44:38.58	SWS	-	-	-	45	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 45ms.
07:44:42.69	SWS	-	100	-	-	Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
07:44:45.60	USH	-	100	-	-	Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
07:44:52.74	USH	-	-	-	5	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
07:44:55.36	USH	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
07:44:55.37	USH	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
07:44:59.44	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 45ms to 50ms.
07:44:59.44	SWS	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 45ms to 50ms.

07:45:02.11	LSH	-	100	-	-	Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
07:45:03.25	LSH	-	-	-	5	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
07:45:06.47	LSH	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 200ms.
07:45:06.47	LSH	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 200ms.
07:45:08.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:45:08.52	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:45:08.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:45:35.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:45:35.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
07:45:36.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:45:40.60	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
07:45:44.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:45:45.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:45:46.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:45:47.66	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:45:48.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:45:50.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:45:51.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:45:51.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:45:57.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:45:57.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:45:57.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:45:57.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:45:59.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:45:59.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:45:59.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:46:01.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:46:02.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:46:03.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:46:05.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:46:12.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Telescope motor initialised.
07:46:19.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Telescope disabled.
07:46:29.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Telescope motor initialised.
07:46:32.46	SWS	-0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
07:46:35.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:46:36.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:46:38.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:46:39.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:46:40.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:46:43.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:46:43.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:47:12.15	---	-	-	-	-	*** had to restart instrument as SWS VIS suddenly dropped out around 7.40
07:47:19.56	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
07:48:19.65	---	-	-	-	-	*** run at 2500 ft
07:50:52.61	---	-	-	-	-	*** for some reason about time has set time to local not zulu
07:51:04.50	---	-	-	-	-	*** zulu is locar plus 3 hours
07:53:43.70	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
07:55:08.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:55:09.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
07:55:09.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:55:13.38	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
07:55:18.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:55:19.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:55:20.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:55:21.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:55:22.35	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:55:24.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:55:25.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:55:26.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:55:27.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:55:28.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:55:30.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:55:33.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:57:32.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:57:32.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
07:57:33.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:57:40.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling

07:57:40.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:57:40.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:57:42.33	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
07:57:45.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:57:45.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:57:45.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:57:46.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:57:46.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:57:47.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:57:47.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:57:47.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:57:48.12	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:57:48.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:57:50.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:57:52.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:57:52.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:57:52.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:57:54.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:57:54.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:57:55.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:01:16.59	---	-	-	-	-	*** 1
08:01:16.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:01:16.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:01:16.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:01:24.04	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
08:02:07.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:02:07.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:02:07.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:02:11.55	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:02:12.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:02:14.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:02:14.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:02:32.99	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
08:03:04.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:03:04.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:03:04.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:03:06.80	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
08:03:08.47	SWS	173.2	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
08:03:09.00	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
08:03:14.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:03:14.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:03:14.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:03:16.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:03:17.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:03:17.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:03:18.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:03:19.77	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:03:22.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:06:03.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:06:03.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:06:03.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:06:05.48	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
08:06:07.14	SWS	-1.6	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
08:06:09.75	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
08:06:14.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:06:14.24	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:06:14.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:06:16.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:06:16.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:06:16.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:06:19.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:06:19.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:06:19.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:06:21.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:06:22.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:06:22.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:06:22.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:06:23.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:06:24.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

08:06:48.42	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
08:10:55.32	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile climb
08:11:11.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:11:11.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:11:11.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:11:12.94	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
08:11:14.59	SWS	169.1	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
08:11:14.66	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
08:11:17.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:11:17.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:11:17.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:11:18.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:11:22.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:11:22.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:11:22.54	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:11:23.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:11:23.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:11:25.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:12:15.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:12:17.66	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:12:18.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:12:19.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:12:20.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:12:21.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:12:41.62	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
08:12:57.58	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile descent
08:15:41.37	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud base around 3.1
08:16:08.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:16:09.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:16:09.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:16:09.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:16:10.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:16:11.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:16:13.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:16:13.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:16:13.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:16:14.37	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:16:14.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:16:16.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:20:48.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:20:48.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:20:48.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:20:51.15	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
08:20:52.84	SWS	-2.6	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
08:20:53.62	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
08:20:56.86	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:20:56.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:20:56.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:20:57.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:21:00.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:21:01.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:21:03.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:21:03.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:21:04.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:21:06.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:21:07.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:21:07.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:21:08.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:21:09.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:21:10.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:21:12.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:21:17.91	---	-	-	-	-	*** run at 500 ft
08:21:25.70	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 3.1
08:30:53.09	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
08:31:58.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:31:59.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:32:00.80	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:32:02.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:32:02.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

08:32:05.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:32:17.38	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile climb (9)
08:34:19.24	---	-	-	-	-	*** below cloud run at 2000 ft
08:34:30.97	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 3.2
08:38:52.62	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
08:39:06.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:39:07.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:39:08.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:39:09.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:43:46.83	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
08:45:01.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:45:02.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:45:03.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:45:04.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:45:05.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:45:08.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:49:36.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:49:37.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:49:38.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:49:39.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:49:40.91	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:49:43.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:52:22.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:52:22.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:52:22.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:52:23.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:52:23.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:52:24.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:52:39.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:52:39.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:52:39.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:52:40.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:52:40.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:52:42.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:58:27.87	---	-	-	-	-	*** 11 deg
09:00:27.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:00:27.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:00:27.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:00:29.47	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
09:00:31.14	SWS	170.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
09:00:31.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:00:31.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:00:31.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:04:26.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:04:26.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:04:26.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:04:27.64	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
09:04:33.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:04:33.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:04:33.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:04:34.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:04:34.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:04:34.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:04:35.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:04:35.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:04:37.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:04:38.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:04:38.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:04:38.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:04:39.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:04:40.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:04:41.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:05:57.86	---	-	-	-	-	*** boundary layer decoupling, q below stratq layer
09:06:10.42	---	-	-	-	-	*** a lot of inhomegeinity in cloud
09:06:24.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:06:24.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:06:24.54	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:06:24.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling

09:06:25.77	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
09:06:27.51	SWS	-5.8	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
09:06:28.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:06:28.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:06:28.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:06:31.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:06:32.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:06:33.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:06:34.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:06:35.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:06:37.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:07:55.52	---	-	-	-	-	*** run at 500 ft below cloud
09:07:58.85	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 4.1
09:15:31.36	---	-	-	-	-	*** 10 deg
09:16:35.40	---	-	-	-	-	*** 11 deg
09:16:42.65	---	-	-	-	-	*** broken cloud above
09:18:18.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:18:19.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:18:20.24	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:18:21.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:18:22.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:18:23.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:18:26.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:18:26.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:18:27.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:18:28.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:18:28.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:18:40.01	---	-	-	-	-	*** climbing to 3900 ft
09:18:52.89	---	-	-	-	-	*** corection 39000
09:21:55.99	---	-	-	-	-	*** run at 39000 in almost cloud free/ scattered cloud conditions
09:22:42.98	---	-	-	-	-	*** recommenceing run at 3000 ft
09:22:52.44	---	-	-	-	-	*** to be below inversion
09:23:12.88	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run now
09:23:19.30	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
09:27:46.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:27:47.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:27:48.62	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:27:49.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:27:50.58	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:27:53.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:27:53.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:27:54.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:27:55.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:27:56.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:27:57.76	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:28:00.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:28:35.41	LSH	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 50ms.
09:28:35.42	LSH	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 50ms.
09:28:37.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:28:38.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:28:40.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:28:41.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:29:37.38	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
09:32:24.69	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
09:32:44.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:32:45.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:32:46.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:32:47.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:32:48.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:32:49.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:33:17.08	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
09:33:22.48	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile climb
09:40:11.17	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13
09:42:37.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:42:38.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:42:38.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:42:39.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:44:16.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

09:44:17.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:44:17.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:44:18.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:45:22.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:45:23.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:45:24.80	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:45:25.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:45:26.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:45:27.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:45:28.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:45:34.04	LSH	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 100ms.
09:45:34.05	LSH	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 100ms.
09:45:35.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:45:37.34	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:45:42.39	LSH	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 200ms.
09:45:42.40	LSH	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 200ms.
09:45:47.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:45:50.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:45:51.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:45:54.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:46:00.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:46:00.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:46:00.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:46:02.14	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
09:46:03.84	SWS	172.3	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
09:46:05.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:46:05.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:46:05.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:46:08.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:46:08.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:46:08.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:46:09.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:46:09.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:46:11.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:46:25.10	---	-	-	-	-	*** descending
09:46:33.92	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile 16
09:47:23.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:47:23.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:47:23.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:47:24.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:47:25.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:47:26.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:48:56.12	LSH	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 400ms.
09:48:56.13	LSH	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 400ms.
09:49:11.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:49:11.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:49:11.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:49:12.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:49:12.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:49:16.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:49:18.72	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
09:49:24.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:49:24.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:49:24.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:49:25.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:49:25.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:49:28.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:51:09.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:51:09.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:51:09.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:51:10.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:51:10.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:51:13.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:51:51.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:51:51.80	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:51:51.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:51:52.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:51:52.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:51:56.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

09:52:03.44	SWS	-	-	30	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 30ms.
09:52:03.45	SWS	-	-	-	30	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 30ms.
09:52:04.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:52:05.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:52:06.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:52:07.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:52:09.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:52:09.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:52:09.93	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:52:10.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:52:10.80	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:52:14.58	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:53:28.85	---	-	-	-	-	*** 11 deg
09:55:55.87	---	-	-	-	-	*** passing through cloud
09:56:28.04	---	-	-	-	-	*** below cloud
09:56:31.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:56:31.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:56:32.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:56:32.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:56:32.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:56:36.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:56:37.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:56:37.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:56:37.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:56:40.36	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
09:56:42.08	SWS	-4.6	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
09:56:42.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:56:42.76	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:56:42.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:56:45.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:56:45.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:56:45.72	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:56:46.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:56:46.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:56:50.52	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:59:39.58	---	-	-	-	-	*** 10 deg
10:00:31.62	---	-	-	-	-	*** 11 deg
10:02:09.81	---	-	-	-	-	*** run at 500 ft (5.1)
10:02:13.46	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
10:03:10.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:03:10.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:03:10.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:03:11.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:03:11.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:03:15.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:03:15.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:03:15.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:03:16.27	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:03:17.39	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
10:03:19.10	SWS	172.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:03:20.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:03:20.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:03:20.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:03:23.77	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:03:23.86	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:03:23.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:03:24.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:03:24.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:03:28.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:05:44.12	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:05:44.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:05:44.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:05:46.77	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
10:05:48.52	SWS	-5.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:05:49.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:05:49.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:05:49.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:05:51.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:05:51.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

10:05:51.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:05:52.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:05:52.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:05:56.58	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:06:06.08	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
10:09:24.24	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
10:11:58.32	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:11:58.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:11:58.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:11:59.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:11:59.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:12:02.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:13:09.68	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile climb (18)
10:14:24.07	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of profile
10:14:53.58	---	-	-	-	-	*** run
10:15:20.22	---	-	-	-	-	*** below cloud run
10:15:56.21	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 5.2
10:25:29.65	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
10:25:35.34	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile climb 19
10:27:11.37	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:27:11.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:27:11.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:27:12.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:27:12.37	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:27:16.24	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:27:38.60	---	-	-	-	-	*** enterin cloud
10:28:23.46	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 5.3 in cloud
10:29:01.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:29:01.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:29:01.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:29:02.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:29:02.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:29:06.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:29:26.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:29:26.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:29:26.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:29:29.22	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
10:29:30.94	SWS	173.3	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:29:32.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:29:32.34	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:29:32.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:29:34.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:29:35.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:29:35.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:29:35.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:29:36.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:29:40.36	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:29:40.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:31:03.47	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:31:03.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:31:03.59	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:31:05.53	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
10:31:07.21	SWS	-4.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:31:08.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:31:08.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:31:08.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:31:10.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:31:10.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:31:10.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:31:11.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:31:11.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:31:15.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:38:16.22	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
10:38:26.30	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile 20 (up)
10:39:29.76	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud top at 48
10:40:05.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:40:05.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:40:05.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:40:08.71	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000

10:40:10.46	SWS	173.8	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:40:11.53	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:40:11.54	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:40:11.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:40:14.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:40:15.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:40:15.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:40:15.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:40:16.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:40:19.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:40:48.39	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile 21 descending
10:41:49.50	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
10:42:02.23	---	-	-	-	-	*** going into cloud
10:42:35.43	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 5.4 in cloud to overpass Ron Brown
10:42:50.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:42:51.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:42:51.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:42:51.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:42:52.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:42:55.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:43:50.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:43:50.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:43:50.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:43:52.54	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
10:43:54.27	SWS	-5.4	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:43:54.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:43:54.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:43:54.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:44:01.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:44:01.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:44:01.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:44:01.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:44:02.57	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:44:05.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:45:57.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:45:57.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:45:58.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:46:00.02	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
10:46:01.75	SWS	173.6	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:46:04.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:46:04.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:46:04.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:46:06.54	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:46:06.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:46:06.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:46:07.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:46:07.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:46:10.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:46:10.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:46:11.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:46:11.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:46:11.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:47:31.74	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
10:47:54.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:47:54.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:47:54.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:47:56.01	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
10:47:57.67	SWS	-3.2	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:47:58.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:47:58.34	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:47:58.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:48:11.90	---	-	-	-	-	*** over ship now
10:48:33.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:48:33.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:48:33.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:48:34.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:48:34.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:48:38.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:50:08.27	---	-	-	-	-	*** 11 deg

10:52:11.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:52:11.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:52:12.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:52:13.94	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
10:52:15.70	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:52:17.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:52:17.12	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:52:17.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:52:36.76	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile ascent
10:53:05.59	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud top 4700 ft
10:53:52.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:53:52.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:53:52.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:53:53.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:53:53.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:53:57.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:54:05.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:54:05.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:54:05.74	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:54:07.62	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
10:54:09.35	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:54:09.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:54:09.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:54:09.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:54:11.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:54:12.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:54:12.05	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:54:12.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:54:12.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:54:16.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:54:22.85	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile descent to 50 ft
10:55:21.41	---	-	-	-	-	*** going through cloud
10:56:49.36	---	-	-	-	-	*** below cloud
11:00:56.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:00:56.36	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:00:56.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:00:57.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:00:57.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:01:01.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:02:56.44	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 6.1 at 500 ft
11:05:36.59	---	-	-	-	-	*** 11 deg
11:06:18.60	---	-	-	-	-	*** 10 deg
11:07:50.39	---	-	-	-	-	*** 11 deg
11:08:33.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:08:33.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:08:33.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:08:34.87	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
11:08:36.54	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
11:08:36.60	SWS	173.7	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:08:40.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:08:40.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:08:40.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:08:42.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:08:42.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:08:42.59	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:08:43.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:08:43.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:08:47.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:11:05.36	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:11:05.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:11:05.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:11:07.55	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
11:11:09.29	SWS	-5.7	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:11:10.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:11:10.66	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:11:10.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:11:12.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:11:12.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:11:12.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

11:11:13.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:11:13.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:11:17.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:12:00.79	---	-	-	-	-	*** 11 deg
11:13:44.29	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile climb
11:16:10.44	---	-	-	-	-	*** run at 2900 ft
11:16:23.94	---	-	-	-	-	*** below cloud run 6.2
11:18:37.25	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
11:21:04.51	---	-	-	-	-	*** skimming bottom of cloud
11:22:12.88	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
11:26:49.25	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile climb to 4300 ft
11:28:26.60	---	-	-	-	-	*** run at 3800 ft in cloud
11:28:34.44	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 6.3
11:29:34.08	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
11:29:37.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:29:37.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:29:37.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:29:38.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:29:39.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:29:42.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:32:33.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:32:33.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:32:34.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:32:35.86	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
11:32:37.59	SWS	173.6	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:32:39.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:32:39.34	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:32:39.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:32:41.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:32:41.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:32:41.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:32:42.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:32:42.66	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:32:46.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:33:16.67	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
11:34:59.02	---	-	-	-	-	*** point A
11:35:34.72	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:35:34.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:35:34.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:35:36.91	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
11:35:38.66	SWS	-5.7	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:35:39.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:35:39.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:35:39.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:35:43.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:35:43.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:35:44.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:35:44.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:35:44.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:35:48.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:36:56.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
11:36:59.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
11:39:24.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:39:24.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:39:24.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:39:25.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:39:25.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:39:29.52	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:39:46.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:39:46.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:39:46.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:39:46.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:39:47.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:39:50.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:39:58.94	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud top at 4200 ft
11:40:37.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:40:37.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:40:37.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:40:38.62	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000

11:40:40.41	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:40:41.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:40:41.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:40:41.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:40:43.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:40:43.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:40:43.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:40:44.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:40:45.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:40:48.61	SWS	-	-	20	-	VIS int.time changed from 30ms to 20ms.
11:40:48.62	SWS	-	-	-	20	NIR int.time changed from 30ms to 20ms.
11:40:48.72	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:40:52.85	USH	-	-	30	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 30ms.
11:40:52.86	USH	-	-	-	30	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 30ms.
11:40:54.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:40:54.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:40:55.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:40:55.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:40:55.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:40:57.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:40:57.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:40:57.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:40:57.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:41:00.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:41:05.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:41:05.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:41:05.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:41:06.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:41:06.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:41:10.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:41:14.68	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:41:14.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:41:14.74	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:41:15.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:41:15.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:41:19.54	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:41:51.13	---	-	-	-	-	*** going into cloud
11:41:57.49	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud top 4200 ft
11:43:15.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:43:15.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:43:15.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:43:17.36	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
11:43:19.11	SWS	-5.8	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:43:20.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:43:20.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:43:20.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:43:22.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:43:22.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:43:22.58	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:43:22.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:43:23.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:43:27.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:46:32.91	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
11:47:02.98	---	-	-	-	-	*** 50 ft
11:47:32.64	---	-	-	-	-	*** run at 500 ft
11:47:43.32	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 7.1
11:49:09.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:49:09.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:49:09.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:49:10.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:49:10.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:49:14.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:49:20.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:49:21.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:49:21.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:49:24.27	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
11:49:26.01	SWS	173.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:49:27.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:49:27.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

11:49:27.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:50:43.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:50:44.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:50:44.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:50:46.10	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
11:50:47.86	SWS	-5.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:50:49.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:50:49.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:50:49.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:50:52.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:50:52.12	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:50:52.47	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:50:52.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:50:53.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:50:56.99	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:51:36.51	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
11:57:03.62	---	-	-	-	-	*** large aerosol increase here
11:57:21.54	---	-	-	-	-	*** ie an increase in number of large aerosol particles
11:57:25.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:57:25.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:57:25.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:57:26.24	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:57:26.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:57:29.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:57:35.36	---	-	-	-	-	*** 11 deg
11:57:39.83	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile climb
11:59:49.66	---	-	-	-	-	*** in cloud run at 3700 ft (run 7.2)
12:00:15.17	---	-	-	-	-	*** run at 7.2 at 3600 ft
12:01:45.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:01:45.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:01:45.35	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:01:45.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:01:46.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:01:50.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:01:51.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:01:51.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:01:52.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:01:53.83	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
12:01:55.51	SWS	172.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:01:56.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:01:56.66	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:01:56.68	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:02:50.00	---	-	-	-	-	*** 11 deg
12:03:14.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:03:14.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:03:14.77	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:03:18.03	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
12:03:19.79	SWS	-5.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:03:20.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:03:20.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:03:20.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:03:25.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:03:25.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:03:26.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:03:26.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:03:27.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:03:30.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:03:34.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:03:34.68	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:03:34.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:03:35.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:03:35.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:03:39.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:03:48.77	---	-	-	-	-	*** 10 deg
12:04:30.97	---	-	-	-	-	*** 11 deg
12:04:34.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:04:34.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:04:34.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

12:04:34.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:04:35.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:04:38.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:04:39.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:04:39.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:04:39.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:04:39.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:05:40.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:05:40.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:05:40.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:05:41.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:05:41.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:05:45.76	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:22:13.96	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg

Flight:

B410

KEY

Not Fitted

Fitted, Not Operated

Duff Data

Minor Problem

OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:

Heimann:

Deiced Temp:

Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:

Buck CR2:

General Eastern:

Johnson Williams:

Nezvorov:

Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:

Forward Facing:

Rearward Facing:

Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:

GIN Applanix:

INU Honeywell:

Radar Altimeter:

RVSM IAS:

RVSM Static Pressure:

XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

HORACE:

AMTG:

AVAPS:

Cabin Pressure:

Printer:

S9 Static Pressure:

Satcom C:

Satcom H (VIRC):

Turb Centre-Static:

Turb Left Right:

Turb Up-Down:

Turb Horizontal Chk:

Turb Vertical Chk:

Weather Radar:

DLUs:

DLU AERACK:

DLU BBR Lower:

DLU BBR Upper:

DLU Core Chem:

DLU Core Consoles:

DLU Port Aft:

DLU Port Fwd:

DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:

BBR (clear) Lower:

BBR (IR) Lower:

BBR (red) Lower:

Upper:

BBR (clear) Upper:

BBR (IR) Upper:

BBR (red) Upper:

ARIES:

DEIMOS:

IR Camera:

JNO2 Lower:

JNO2 Upper:

JO1D Lower:

JO1D Upper:

MARSS:

SHIMS Lower:

SHIMS Upper:

SWS:

TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

2DC:

2DP:

FFSSP:

PCASP:

PCASP SPP-200:

2DS:

ADA:

CAPS:

CCN:

CDP (fuselage):

CDP (Canister):

CIP 100 (PIP):

CIP 25 (CIP):

CPI:

CVI (Inlet):

CVI PCASP-X:

CVI Ly-A Hygro:

FSSP (UMan):

SID1:

SID2:

SID3:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:

CPC 3786 H2O:

Filters 47mm:

Filters 90mm:

Neph - Dry:

Neph - Wet:

PSAP:

AMS:

CPC (AMS):

SMPS (AMS):

CPC 3010A (CVI):

INC:

Mini-LIDAR:

SP2:

UHSAS:

VACC:

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:

NOx TE42C:

Ozone TE49C:

Ozone TE49:

SO2 TE43C:

TDLAS (NIR) CH4:

TDLAS (NIR) CO2:

FAGE:

Formaldehyde:

NOx FAAM:

NOxy:

ORAC:

PAN:

PERCA:

Peroxide:

PTRMS:

TDLAS (1C):

WAS Bags:

WAS Bottles:

Misc Non-Core

CASI/ATM:

LIDAR (big):

LTI:

SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B410

Date: 29/oct/08

Instruments

CVI -	ok (no CPC)
Neph	ok
PSAP	ok
WetNeph	mostly ok – some comms problems persist
Filters	pipework needs cleaning
SWS -	ok, using manual shutter control
SHIMS -	upper ok Lower not working
AMS	ok
Core Chem -	CO good, using manual cals SO2 ok Nox ok O3 ok
Cloud physics -	PCASP needs cleaning FSSP ok
ARIES -	ok
MARSS -	run unmanned
CCN -	no data on outbound leg, good data on return
VACC -	good operation
2DS -	ok
CAPS -	ok
SMPS -	ok
Buck -	not operated

Aircraft

ISDN Emails

1 email

MPDS

Run for approx 4 hours

Satcom-H Calls

nil

Issues

Upper BBRs need cleaning before every flight

Pre-Flighter's Log

Date: 22/10/23

Flight No: B410

Pre-Flighter: E. Horton

No.	√ or x	Location	Action	Comments
1	☒	Hangar	Collect spanners for core chem	
<u>Aircraft Cabin: Power-up</u>				
2	☒	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	<u>Doug</u>
3	☐	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	☒	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	<u>J. Doug</u>
5	☒	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	
6	☒	Aft CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
7	☒	Fore CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
8	☒	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
9	☒	HORACE	Recording data	
10	☒	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
11	☒	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
12	☒	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
13	☒	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	
14	☒	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
15	☒	Video Laptop	Checked onboard	
16	☒	FWVS	Set up & check on AUTO	<u>Left to operator</u>
17	☒	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked then OFF	
18	☒	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
19	☒	TWC	Fitted & signals checked	
20	☒	GE	Balance checked then back to DP	
21	☒	GPS (XR5M)	Checked	
22	☒	Satcom C	Checked	
23	☒	Video x 2	Records okay <u>rewind</u>	

No.	√ or x	Location	Action	Comments
24	☒	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	In cockpit
25	☐	CNC	Butanol filled	} <u>to fit to operator</u>
26	☐	Dry Neph	Power up & Zero Cal	
27	☐	PSAP	Pre-flight log actions complete	
28	☐	CGPS	CBs and PC ON	
<u>External Checks</u>				
29	☒	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
30	☒	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
31	☒	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
32	☒	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	☐	Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
34	☒	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
35	☒	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	<u>Avalon have also cleaned upper BBRs</u>
36	☒	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
37	☒	Heimann	Lens checked OK	
38	☒	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
39	☒	All other covers	Removed	
40	☐	Pre-flight Bag	Returned to hold	** Check no butanol**
41	☐	Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
42	☐	Tools	Avalon informed	
<u>Avalon Checks</u>				<u>Signed</u>
44	☐	Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		
45	☐	ICEX applied		
46	☐	Turb Probe - Traps emptied, detail contents -		a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) 1/4 full or more
47	☐	Turb Probe - Traps dried and resealed		

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B410:

Log	Reason
Instrument Status	may not be correct – Flight Manager asked to check
Cloud Physics Processing	No cloud physics processing logs are expected for VOCALS flights
MARSS	no log taken, operator was ill
VACC	Operator does not create a log sheet
2D-S / CAPS / CPI	2D-S / CAPS / CPI operator does not create a log sheet
AMS log	AMS operator does not create a log sheet
Buck Hygro note:	Buck not started until after take-off today - forgot about until seat belts were on for taxi. Initially network cable was loose but taped in place and Buck software restarted and running before belts on again.

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	17 Feb 2009	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

Digital video recordings in avi format:

faam-video-dfc_faam_20081029_r0_b410_095641_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20081029_r0_b410_105641_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20081029_r0_b410_115641_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20081029_r0_b410_125641_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20081029_r0_b410_135641_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20081029_r0_b410_145641_1hz.avi

faam-video-rfc_faam_20081029_r0_b410_095655_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20081029_r0_b410_105655_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20081029_r0_b410_115655_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20081029_r0_b410_125655_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20081029_r0_b410_135655_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20081029_r0_b410_145655_1hz.avi

faam-video-ffc_faam_20081029_r0_b410_095651_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20081029_r0_b410_105651_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20081029_r0_b410_115651_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20081029_r0_b410_125651_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20081029_r0_b410_135651_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20081029_r0_b410_145651_1hz.avi

faam-video-ufc_faam_20081029_r0_b410_095700_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20081029_r0_b410_105700_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20081029_r0_b410_115700_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20081029_r0_b410_125700_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20081029_r0_b410_135700_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20081029_r0_b410_145700_1hz.avi

No Digital8 video recordings were made on this flight.